

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 883075.

METICOS

A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Deliverable D6.2

Social data analysis and extracted perceptions

Editor(s):	Sarang Shaikh, Sule Yildirim Yayilgan, Mohamed Abomhara, Erjon Zoto
Responsible Partner:	NTNU
Status-Version:	Final – Version 1
Date:	29 th November 2021
Distribution level (CO, PU):	Public

Copyright message

© METICOS Consortium, 2021

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Project Number:	GA 883075
Project Title:	METICOS

Title of Deliverable:	D6.2: Social data analysis and extracted perceptions
Due Date of Delivery to the EC:	30/11/2021 (M15)

Workpackage responsible for the Deliverable:	WP6 – METICOS Social Toolkit, workshops and recommendations on how to improve the perception of the EU abroad
Editor(s):	Sarang Shaikh, Sule Yildirim Yayilgan, Mohamed Abomhara, Erjon Zoto; NTNU
Contributor(s):	
Reviewer(s):	Lazaros Georgiades; Maria Eirini Koulouri; CYPOL Olha Tytovets; ASBGS All partners
Approved by:	All partners
Recommended/mandatory readers:	All WPs

Abstract:	In the task 6.2, the methods for analysing social data will be listed. Namely, after identifying the possible sources of information and depending on the nature of the specified social sources (oral, written means etc.) methods for gathering the information will be listed. Examples according to the specified source will be given. The outcome of the specified task will be documented in the report D6.2.
------------------	--

Keyword List:	social data analysis, social media data, NLP, machine learning, deep learning, perception extraction, user perceptions, METICOS, WP6.
Disclaimer	This deliverable reflects only the author’s views and views and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein

Document Description

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
v0.1	15/08/2021	Table of contents	NTNU
v0.2	08/11/2021	Draft Submission to EUC	NTNU
V0.3	15/11/2021	Perception extraction draft	NTNU
V0.4	23/11/2021	Submission to the internal reviewers	NTNU
V0.5	28/11/2021	Addressing the reviews from VUB, ICCS	NTNU
V1.0	29/11/2021	Final version ready for submission	NTNU
V1.1	30/11/2021	Final version addressing the final comments	NTNU

Table of Contents

List of Figures.....	6
List of Tables.....	7
Terms and abbreviations.....	8
Executive Summary	9
1 Introduction.....	10
1.1 Main purpose and objectives	10
1.2 Document Outline	12
2 Social Media Sources and Data	12
2.1 Social Media Sources.....	12
2.1.1 Twitter	12
2.1.2 Facebook	13
2.1.3 Reddit	13
2.1.4 LinkedIn	13
2.2 Social Media Data.....	13
2.2.1 Structured Data	14
2.2.2 Unstructured Data.....	14
2.2.3 Semi-Structured Data	14
3 Methods for gathering social media data	15
3.1 Data gathering via tools	15
3.1.1 Free Accessible Tools.....	15
A. Web Scraper/Crawler	15
B. Google Trends	15
C. Google Analytics	17
3.1.2 Commercial Tools.....	17
I. BirdIQ.....	17
II. Tweet Binder	17
3.2 Data access via Application Programming Interfaces (APIs).....	17
3.2.1 Types of APIs	18
1) Open APIs	18
2) Internal APIs	18
3.2.2 Common Social Media Data APIs	18
a. Twitter API.....	18
b. Facebook API	20

4	Techniques and methods for analysing the social media data	22
4.1	Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques and methods for analysing social media data	22
4.1.1	Machine Learning (ML).....	23
1)	Supervised Learning	24
2)	Unsupervised Learning.....	24
3)	Semi-Supervised Learning	25
4)	Performance metrics for Learning Methods	27
4.1.2	Deep Learning (DL)	28
1.	Deep Supervised Learning	30
2.	Deep Unsupervised Learning.....	30
3.	Deep Semi-Supervised Learning.....	30
4.1.3	Natural Language Processing (NLP).....	31
4.1.4	NLP Techniques	35
I.	Sentiment Analysis Techniques.....	35
II.	Topic Modelling.....	38
III.	Subjectivity Analysis	40
IV.	Intent Detection	41
V.	Keyword/Keyphrase Extraction.....	41
5	Perception Extraction from Social Media Data	43
6	Existing application areas for perception extraction from social media data.....	44
7	METICOS and Border Control Technologies on social media platforms	45
8	Perception extraction about the METICOS and Border Control Technologies	45
9	Preliminary Results.....	46
9.1	Keywords Analysis	47
9.1.1	Possible bias in keyword analysis	47
9.2	Data Collection	48
9.2.1	Pseudonymization and Anonymization techniques to handle data privacy for collected data in perception extraction architecture pipeline	50
9.2.2	Possible bias in data collection.....	52
9.2.3	Possible bias in data pre-processing	53
9.3	Experiments.....	54
9.3.1	Possible bias in experiments	54
9.3.2	Subjectivity Classification	55
9.3.3	Intent Classification	56
9.3.4	Sentiment Analysis	56

9.3.5	Keyword/Keyphrase Extraction	57
9.3.6	Aspect Classification	57
9.4	Results	58
9.4.1	Bias in perception extraction results.....	58
9.4.2	Perception Extraction Results	59
10	Relevance of the results in T6.3	65
11	Conclusion	66
	References.....	67
	Appendix.....	76

List of Figures

FIGURE 1	OVERVIEW OF D6.2 AND MAPPING WITH T6.3	11
FIGURE 2	TYPES OF SOCIAL MEDIA DATA	14
FIGURE 3	TAXONOMY OF METHODS FOR GATHERING SOCIAL MEDIA DATA	15
FIGURE 4	EXAMPLE OF GOOGLE TRENDS OUTPUT	16
FIGURE 5	NORMAL WORKFLOW OF AN API.....	18
FIGURE 6	FACEBOOK GRAPH API FLOW.....	21
FIGURE 7	TYPES OF AI TECHNIQUES	22
FIGURE 8	TAXONOMY OF ML.....	24
FIGURE 9	COMMON ML FLOW	25
FIGURE 10	BASIC ARCHITECTURE OF A SIMPLE DNN	29
FIGURE 11	TAXONOMY OF DL.....	29
FIGURE 12	FROM UNSTRUCTURED TO STRUCTURED DATA USING NLP	32
FIGURE 13	TEXT PRE-PROCESSING TECHNIQUES IN NLP	33
FIGURE 14	EXAMPLE OF FEATURE ENGINEERING	34
FIGURE 15	TAXONOMY OF NLP TECHNIQUES FOR PERCEPTION EXTRACTION	35
FIGURE 16	TAXONOMY OF SENTIMENT ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES.....	36
FIGURE 17	WORD CLOUD SHOWING EXTRACTED TOPICS FROM THE TWITTER AGAINST COVID-19 [110]	38
FIGURE 18	TOPIC MODELLING APPROACHES	39
FIGURE 19	KEYWORD/KEYPHRASE EXTRACTION SOTA APPROACHES	42
FIGURE 20	PERCEPTION EXTRACTION PIPELINE FOR BORDER CONTROL TECHNOLOGIES	46
FIGURE 21	TECHNOLOGICAL DETAILS FOR PERCEPTION EXTRACTION COMPONENTS	46
FIGURE 22	BORDER CONTROL TECHNOLOGIES KEYWORDS' TRENDS ON GOOGLE WEB SEARCH	48
FIGURE 23	BORDER CONTROL TECHNOLOGIES KEYWORDS' POPULARITY FOR PAST 05 YEARS	48
FIGURE 24	DATA COLLECTION SAMPLE	49
FIGURE 25	SBC KEYWORDS FOR TWITTER	50
FIGURE 26	YEARWISE COUNT OF TWEETS.....	50
FIGURE 27	FLOW OF SUBJECTIVITY CLASSIFICATION TECHNIQUE	56
FIGURE 28	FLOW OF INTENT CLASSIFICATION TECHNIQUE	56
FIGURE 29	FLOW OF SENTIMENT ANALYSIS TECHNIQUE	57

FIGURE 30 FLOW OF KEYWORD/KEYPHRASE EXTRACTION TECHNIQUE	57
FIGURE 31 FLOW OF ASPECT CLASSIFICATION TECHNIQUE	58
FIGURE 32 PREDICTED SENTIMENTS DISTRIBUTION	60
FIGURE 33 MOST FREQUENT USER LOCATIONS.....	61
FIGURE 34 MOST FREQUENT LOCATIONS-BASED USER SENTIMENTS.....	61
FIGURE 35 YEAR WISE TWEETS DISTRIBUTION	62
FIGURE 36 YEAR-WISE SENTIMENTS DISTRIBUTION	62
FIGURE 37 KEYWORD/KEYPHRASE EXTRACTION RESULTS	63
FIGURE 38 ASPECT’S CLASSIFICATION RESULTS	63
FIGURE 39 ASPECT CLASSIFICATION WITH SENTIMENTS RESULTS	64
FIGURE 40 INTENT CLASSIFICATION RESULTS	64
FIGURE 41 OVERALL METICOS SOCIAL SENSING TOOLKIT ARCHITECTURE	66

List of Tables

TABLE 1 TWITTER API VERSIONS	19
TABLE 2 TYPES OF FACEBOOK API	20
TABLE 3: STATE-OF-THE-ART OF ML MODELS FOR ANALYSING SOCIAL MEDIA DATA.....	25
TABLE 4: STATE-OF-THE-ART OF DL MODELS FOR ANALYSING SOCIAL MEDIA DATA.....	30
TABLE 5: TEXT PARSING TECHNIQUES FOR NLP	33
TABLE 6 STATE-OF-THE-ART SENTIMENT ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES.....	37
TABLE 7 RECENT TOPIC MODELLING APPROACHES	40
TABLE 8: STATE-OF-THE-ART OF SUBJECTIVITY ANALYSIS APPROACHES.....	41
TABLE 9 STATE-OF-THE-ART OF INTENT DETECTION APPROACHES	41
TABLE 10 STATE-OF-THE-ART OF KEYWORD/KEYPHRASE EXTRACTION APPROACHES.....	43
TABLE 11 PERCEPTION EXTRACTION FROM SOCIAL MEDIA APPLICATION AREAS	44
TABLE 12 METICOS SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS INFORMATION	45
TABLE 13 INPUT PROVIDED TO TWITTER ACADEMIC SEARCH API	48
TABLE 14 META DATA RETRIEVED FROM TWITTER API FOR EACH TWEET.....	49

Terms and abbreviations

SoTA	State-of-the-art
ML	Machine Learning
DL	Deep Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
DNN	Deep Neural Networks
RNN	Recurrent Neural Networks
LSTM	Long-Short Term Memory
Bi-LSTM	Bidirectional LSTM
BCPs	Border crossing points
SBC	Smart border control
ABC	Automatic border control
JSON	JavaScript object notation
XML	Extensible markup language
APIs	Application programming interface
HTML	Hypertext markup language
CSS	Cascading style sheets
SEO	Search engine optimizations
HTTP	Hypertext transfer protocol
AI	Artificial intelligence
SVM	Support vector machine
NB	NaiveBayes
DT	DecisionTree
RF	RandomForest
KNN	K NearestNeighbour
LR	LogisticRegression
MRF	Markov random field
BoW	Bag of Words
LDA	Linear discriminant analysis
CNN	Convolutional neural networks
ANN	Artificial neural networks
DenseNets	Dense networks
MLP	Multi-layer perceptron
POS	Parts of speech
TFIDF	Term frequency – inverse document frequency
SA	Sentiment analysis
OM	Opinion mining
LSA	Latent semantic analysis
NNMF	Non-negative matrix factorization
PLSA	Probabilistic latent semantic analysis
LDA	Latent Dirichlet allocation
NLU	Natural language understanding
e-gates	Electronic gates
ETIAS	European travel information and authorisation system

Executive Summary

Deliverable D6.2 provides state-of-the-art (SoTA) for the possible social media sources along with different types of social data as well as methods for gathering data from social media sources. Furthermore, this deliverable also provides SoTA review of the techniques available for analysing social media data. This deliverable links all of the SoTA discussions to the “perception extraction”, which is one of the key components involved in developing METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit for predicting technology acceptance of the automatic border control technologies. Beyond discussing the SoTA studies and perception extraction, this deliverable also discusses the perception extraction architecture pipeline designed for extracting perceptions for border control technologies from social media data as a part of T6.2. The preliminary implementations, experiments and results for perception extraction pipeline are also discussed in this deliverable (6.2). However, the more in detail discussions will be reported in the future deliverable (D6.3).

The current deliverable report consists of eleven sections: Section 1 presents an introduction including the primary purposes, objectives and document outline. Section 2 provides a more general overview of the social media sources and social media data. Section 3 provides an in-depth review of different methods available for gathering social media data. Section 4 provides detailed overview as well as a SOTA review in AI techniques used for analysing social media data such as machine learning, deep learning and natural language processing. Section 5 and 6 discuss the perception extraction from the social media data and review the SoTA studies for perception extraction. Section 7 lists the major social media platforms where METICOS has an official group or page available for dissemination activities. Section 8 shows the proposed perception extraction architecture pipeline as a part of T6.2 to extract user perceptions for border control technologies along with architecture’s technical and implementation details as well. Section 9 discuss some of the preliminary results obtained with the proposed perception extraction architecture. Section 10 shows the mapping/relevance of the perception extraction results with METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit. Section 11 concludes the overall contribution of the deliverable.

Due to the lack of bibliographical references about the implementation of perception extraction from social media data for border control technologies, D6.2 will be used as a guide for the following tasks of WP6, T6.2 (methods for gathering and analysing social media data) and T6.3 (METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit).

1 Introduction

1.1 Main purpose and objectives

METICOS aims to introduce Big Data Analysis for border control information systems, to provide a step-change towards more modern and efficient Smart Border management as well as towards gaining societal and political acceptance of modern control technologies of EU borders such as “no gate solutions”. Therefore, It is positioned as an initiative to create a real-time decision-support system with regard to different Smart Border control technologies in order to ensure user acceptance, secure positive societal impact and maximize border control process efficiency. To this end, the METICOS project will develop a platform that integrates information systems and networks of data sources in order to validate the efficiency and users’ acceptance of border control technologies.

Deliverable D6.2 provides a survey and state of the art (SoTA) of possible social media sources which can be used for the METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit. Specifically, T6.2 is mainly related to activities such as SoTA of methods available for gathering social media data and techniques to analyse and extract user perceptions from the social media data. Beyond discussing the SoTA methods/techniques, this deliverable (6.2) also discusses a perception extraction architecture pipeline for border control technologies based on SoTA techniques. Furthermore, this deliverable also shows the preliminary implementations and experimental details for the proposed perception extraction pipeline along with some initial perception extraction results.

In this context, this report’s main objectives are:

- To present an overview about possible social media sources, types of social media data and methods for gathering social media data
- To present in depth SoTA for different techniques available for analysing and extracting perceptions from the social media data
- To explain the challenges identified from brief SoTA for perception extraction from social media data for border control technologies
- To present a new pipeline architecture for perception extraction from social media data for border control technologies.
- To discuss the preliminary selected techniques/algorithms along with experimental/implementation details for the components involved in the proposed perception extraction architecture pipeline.
- To show the preliminary results generated by collecting border control technologies’ social media data and processing the collected data from the perception extraction pipeline.
- To discuss the relevance of work done in the T6.2 with the T6.3
- To conclude the overall D6.2 work.

To achieve the main objectives of Task 6.2 and D6.2, Figure 1 presents the main steps for the tasks involved in overall T6.2.

1. Acquire knowledge: In this step, we conducted a theoretical SoTA study to gain a comprehensive understanding for: 1) social media sources, 2) social media data, 3) methods for gathering social media data, 4) techniques for analysing social media data and 5) perception extraction from social media data. Books, scientific papers (e.g., conferences,

journals and technical reports), strategy reports and policy documents served as various sources of knowledge.

2. Perception extraction architecture (border control technologies): In this step, we started with doing practical tasks in order to design a perception extraction architecture pipeline for border control technologies. We started with: 1) selection of the social media source to use for the preliminary experiments, 2) identification of social media data needs to be extracted, 3) selection of the techniques/algorithms for perception extraction for border control technologies and 4) defining overall pipeline flow of the perception extraction architecture.
3. Executing architecture pipeline: In this step, we conducted preliminary experiments using all the practical steps defined in step 2 for extracting users' perceptions from social media data for the border control technologies.
4. Discussion and reporting of the results: In this step, we discuss the results obtained by performing experiments in step 3. The preliminary experiments and results are discussed in D6.2 but the in detail final results will be discussed in the D6.3.
5. Evaluation: In this step, we evaluate the perception extraction results by mapping/integrating them into T6.3 (METICOS Social Sending Toolkit architecture) to enhance the technology acceptance prediction.

Figure 1 Overview of D6.2 and mapping with T6.3

1.2 Document Outline

The remaining part of this report is structured as follows:

- **Section 2** (Social Media Sources and Data) provides an overview of possible social media sources used for gathering and analysing social media data. Also, it discusses the different type of social media data available such as: structured data, unstructured data and semi-structured data.
- **Section 3** (Methods for gathering social media data) presents different SOTA methods available for gathering data from various social media platforms.
- **Section 4** explains SOTA techniques for analysing social media data along with existing studies. Specifically, this section focuses on Artificial Intelligence techniques (5.1) like machine learning (5.1.1), deep learning (5.1.2) and natural language processing (5.1.3., 5.1.4).
- **Section 5** discusses the perception extraction from social media data
- **Section 6** explains different SOTA studies and domains where perception extraction from social media data is used.
- **Section 7** lists the various social media platforms containing official METICOS group/page.
- **Section 8** explains the proposed perception extraction architecture for border control technologies in detail, which is used for T6.2.
- **Section 9** discusses the preliminary results of the extracted perceptions for border control technologies.
- **Section 10** shows the relevance of the extracted perceptions for T6.3 (METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit).
- **Section 11** offers a summary of the main ideas and the finding of our research in form of conclusion.

2 Social Media Sources and Data

This section explains the possible social media platforms, which we have used to extract users' perceptions regarding border control technologies. There are several sites that users utilize to interact with each other including (not limited to) Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, TikTok, Pinterest, Snapchat, LinkedIn, Reddit, Taringa etc. In the following, we discuss a few of these social media platforms.

2.1 Social Media Sources

2.1.1 Twitter

Twitter is a microblogging social media platform having more than 192 million daily active users as of last quarter of 2020 and is growing very fast [1]. The users are allowed to write any post or message called "tweet" about any topic up to the limit of 140 characters. The data sharing model of twitter is very simple and flexible; a user does not need to follow-back to the user whom it follows. Therefore, it is one of the most dynamic social media platforms in terms of user interaction and data sharing. Compared to other social media platforms like facebook or instagram, it has a straightforward data access API to get the social media content about specific topics. Although the data access APIs are premium, the free API has a lot of features available.

2.1.2 Facebook

Facebook has indeed various tools that provide a medium for social sensing. Opinion Polls, for example, are platforms that allow users to survey their friends' opinions. Facebook also has Hashtag Pages, similar to Twitter, where Facebook posts labelled with a specific keyword are collected in a single Facebook page, and the available data can be used for social sensing. However, more importantly, the most authentic Facebook social sensing mechanism is based on user interactions via user walls, which are Facebook pages where users can add comments or like posts shared by their friends. The discussion of the opinions through these interactions on Facebook results in a comment thread, which is a collection of user posts [2]. The comment thread is a medium for social sensing since it facilitates the collection of the opinions of Facebook users on a specific event, which may be estimated using the posts in the comment thread.

2.1.3 Reddit

Reddit is a social news aggregation, discussion based online social media platform. The members are allowed to post content on the site such as links, texts, images, and videos, which are rated and voted by other members. The posts are organized into user-created categories called subreddits, which cover a variety of topics such as news, politics, health, technology etc. [3]. The posts with highest votes or ratings appear on the top of specific subreddit. As of September 2021, this platform is the 19th most visited social media platform world-wide. Most of its visitors are from United States. This platform was founded by University of Virginia in October, 2006¹.

2.1.4 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a business-oriented social networking site that was created in 2003 with the goal of allowing registered users to maintain a list of contact details of people they know and trust in business, referred to as connections. The user's social network is determined by their list of connections. Each registered user gives free text for both personal and professional information. Specialities (professional skills), Interests, and Groups and Associations affiliated with the user, are frequently exploited among professional data, which have been proved very important sources for improving collaborative filtering systems [4].

2.2 Social Media Data

This section presents a brief discussion on the type of data which could be collected from the social media – structured data, semi-structured data and unstructured data as shown in Figure 2.

¹ <https://www.alex.com/siteinfo/reddit.com>

Figure 2 Types of social media data

2.2.1 Structured Data

Structured data is a data that uses a pre-defined data model and is in form of tabular format with relationship between the different rows and columns. The common examples of structured data are SQL databases and excel or csv files. All of these have pre-defined rows and columns data model structure. Due to the pre-defined data models, each field is discrete and can be accessed separately or jointly along with data from other fields. This makes structured data extremely powerful [5]. Common examples of structured data in social media are user accounts and posts data stored on social media platforms servers.

2.2.2 Unstructured Data

Unstructured data is a data that is either not organized into any pre-defined manner or does not have any data model representation. Unstructured data is always text-heavy, but may contain data such as images, videos and audios. The irregularities and ambiguities in unstructured data make it difficult to process via traditional structured techniques. The ability to store and process unstructured data has greatly grown in recent years, with many new technologies and tools coming to the market that are able to store specialized types of unstructured data like MongoDB [6]. Common examples of structured data in social media are text, images involved in user posts.

2.2.3 Semi-Structured Data

Semi-structured data is a form of structured data that does not conform with the formal structure of data models associated with relational databases or other forms of data tables, but nonetheless contain tags or other markers to separate semantic elements and enforce hierarchies of records and fields within the data. Therefore, it is also known as self-describing structure [7]. Examples of semi-structured data include JSON and XML are forms of semi-structured data.

3 Methods for gathering social media data

This section explains various methods available for gathering data related to user profiles and users' shared content from social media platforms listed in section 2. Figure 3 shows the taxonomy of various data gathering methods from the social media platforms.

Figure 3 Taxonomy of methods for gathering social media data

3.1 Data gathering via tools

3.1.1 Free Accessible Tools

A. Web Scraper/Crawler

Web scrapers/crawlers are small software programs, designed in a way that can copy data from any publicly available online website. These crawlers can copy all the text from the pages they visit during their execution [8]. The required content of the page is identified by several relevant HTML and CSS tags from the source code of the page. The major drawback of these crawlers is each time for each different web page the source code of the software needs to be re-written according to the webpage structure. It is recommended to use this method if one needs to get data from a limited number of websites, otherwise for getting data from a complete world wide web (www) it is not recommended. Several programming languages such as Python, Java, PHP provide built-in support for writing these web scrapers using their libraries including (but not limited to) BeautifulSoup², ScrapingBee³, PHPScraper⁴, respectively.

B. Google Trends

Google trends⁵ is a free web-based platform provided and supported by one of the leading search engine Google⁶. This website analyses the popularity of different search queries in google search and its relevant websites performed by several users worldwide. Google trends provides output

² <https://pypi.org/project/beautifulsoup4/>

³ <https://www.scrapingbee.com/>

⁴ <https://phpscraper.de/>

⁵ <https://trends.google.com/trends/>

⁶ <https://www.google.com>

in terms of graphs, charts and tables to show the popularity of any search query. Google Trends has been widely used for forecasting economic indicators in financial markets [9, 10]. Also, in the past it was Google Trends data which detected the regional flu cases before traditional monitoring systems [11]. Figure 4 shows the example output of the Google Trends website for the query “border control”. As you can see, this website shows many details regarding the trend of searching “border control” keyword by showing searches done by time, by region, related topics and related queries. The timeline for getting trends was set from “01/12/2019” to “01/01/2021”. This gives evidence such that before going to search relevant keywords on the social media platforms for getting social media data, one can verify the trends of the selected keywords and also get more relevant queries and topics as well.

Figure 4 Example of Google Trends Output

C. Google Analytics

Google Analytics⁷ is a web-based analytics service which provides statistics and data analytics tool for SEO and marketing purpose. It is a part of Google Marketing Platform and is free to anyone having Google organizational account. This tool is mainly used to assess website performance and track visitor insights for a specific website. It helps organizations to determinate top user traffics, marketing activities and campaigns, users trends based on different demographics. Many of the organizations either small, medium, or big use this tool to analysed customer behaviours, which ultimately improves their organizational policies.

3.1.2 Commercial Tools

I. BirdIQ

BirdIQ⁸ is a commercial tool for collecting data from the Twitter. It uses the Twitter API to communicate with Twitter. This tool has a very user friendly interface for defining query keywords to search from the twitter. It provides historical as well as real-time data collection from the Twitter. All of the pricing plans of this tool are free for first seven days only [12].

II. Tweet Binder

TweetBinder⁹ is a well-known commercial tool for social media data management with over 16M users. The tool is ideal for small-medium sized businesses. This tool allows the businesses to generate analytics report by tracking different hashtags [13].

3.2 Data access via Application Programming Interfaces (APIs)

An application programming interface, or API, enables different online web and social media platforms to make their data accessible to different external third-party individuals and companies to access their data via an authorised way. These APIs are implemented using different computer programs which send requests to the online platforms and receive the required data in return. The major difference between an API and web scraper is that API is a standard to get the required data and the data retrieved using an API is more quality data as compared to the web scraper. The users of an API do not need to know how an API is designed; they simply use the documented interface to send requests and receive required data in return [14]. Figure 5 shows the normal standard workflow of an API where a web application from the browser requests the already built-in API for some data access. The API goes through the organization web server, database and returns the requested data in response to the web application in the browser.

⁷ <https://analytics.google.com>

⁸ <https://birdiq.net/pricing>

⁹ <https://www.tweetbinder.com/>

Figure 5 Normal Workflow of an API

3.2.1 Types of APIs

The main types of commonly used APIs are:

1) Open APIs

These are the open-source APIs which can be accessed via HTTP protocols. The endpoints for these APIs are already defined by their developers in the form of request and response formats. These are public APIs. A collective list of free APIs for use in software and web development are presented in¹⁰.

2) Internal APIs

These are APIs that are not publicly available and are hidden from external users. These APIs are organization specific and each of the organizations design it in their own way. Any user who wants to access data of the companies, needs to request for specific endpoints of request and response from the technical department of the companies. These APIs are usually free for accessing small amounts of data but if a user needs more information, needs to purchase the API from the company. One example of these APIs is the “News API”¹¹ from Thomson & Reuters which provides access to online news based on specific query search.

3.2.2 Common Social Media Data APIs

Most of the social media platforms make available their platforms’ data regarding usage patterns through their APIs. Hence, this provides an interface to the researchers to collect data regarding specific social media platforms. These APIs provide contributions for several opportunities for both qualitative and quantitative research by providing access to digital footprints of different users which reveals to the usage patterns, communications, connectivity in greater details. Most of the time, the social media platforms provide their relevant APIs endpoint as free to access the limited amount of data. But if anyone requires more information, the API needs to be purchased. Sometimes, the social media platforms also provide free access to their large amount of data. This option is only valid if any one needs the data for some research purpose [15, 16]. Some of the common social media data APIs are discussed below.

a. Twitter API¹²

The twitter API enables to harness the power of “Twitter” social media platform by giving its global, open, historical, and real-time communications data from its platform. Through its API, twitter provides a list of several endpoints which can be used to access the users’ tweets by defining relevant

¹⁰ <https://github.com/public-apis/public-apis>

¹¹ <https://newsapi.org/>

¹² <https://developer.twitter.com>

keywords. The current version of the twitter API is the “Twitter API v2: Early Access¹³”. With this API version, we can search, retrieve, and analyse the public conversation related to several topics being discussed on twitter. The major benefits to new version of the API as compared to the previous version are supported to request specific data fields, new and updated data objects, tweets’ metric returns, tweet topics with annotations and many more. Mainly, there are two types of searches that usually one can perform using twitter API.

- Historical / Archival Search API¹⁴

This search API offers two endpoints which allows you to search tweets: 1) Recent search and 2) Full-archive search. Both endpoints consist of the same design and architecture while retrieving data including searching tweets via keywords. Additionally, both endpoints support various filter features like language, location, date, etc. The major difference between both endpoints is the limit of accessing past data. Recent searches can only access data back to 30 days from the date of search. However, full-archive search can access data back to the first tweet since March 2006 from the date of search.

- Real Time Streaming API¹⁵

This search API allows users to fetch real-time tweets from twitter at any given instance of time. Using this search API, we can easily get the new tweets about any selected topic in real-time whenever it is posted on twitter. There are two major endpoints in this search API: 1) Sampled Stream and 2) Filtered Stream. The sampled stream endpoint returns a roughly 1% of random tweets from the real-time public tweets. However, the filtered stream endpoint enables developers to filter the real-time public tweets based on various filters like language, location, device type, etc. There different versions of twitter API and their statistics are mentioned below in Table 1.

Table 1 Twitter API Versions

Variant	Features	Price	Types
Twitter API v2: Early Access ¹³	Support users as well as tweets search Supports recent as well as full historical search Supports real-time tweets search Pull new metrics Receive new Tweet annotations fields in responses, and filter search queries based on this data	Free	Standard Search API <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Query length of 512 characters • Historical data upto 30 days • 500000 tweets per month • 1 project per API Academic Search API <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Query length of 1024 characters • Historical data upto March 2006 • 1000000 tweets per month • More than 1 project

¹³ <https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/twitter-api/early-access>

¹⁴ <https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/twitter-api/tweets/search/introduction>

¹⁵ <https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/twitter-api/tweets/sampled-stream/introduction>

	Receive standardized JSON data response		per API
Standard v1.1 ¹⁶	Support users as well as tweets search Supports recent as well as full historical search Supports real-time tweets search	Free	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Query length of 512 characters • Historical data upto 7 days
Premium v1.1 ¹⁷	Support users as well as tweets search Supports recent as well as full historical search Supports real-time tweets search	Paid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Query length of 1024 characters • Historical data upto 30 days or full archive search • Different pricing for historical data search

b. Facebook API¹⁸

Facebook APIs are the primary method to connect with the Facebook social media platform. There are several APIs offered by Facebook to get insights from users' data posting and commenting on the platform. Few of the common APIs offered from the Facebook are as presented in Table 2. Because the Facebook Graph API is the most widely used API to read and write posts from Facebook; we will discuss this in more detail.

Table 2 Types of Facebook API

API	Purpose
Facebook Live API ¹³	Facebook video LIVE API allows the developer to perform live streaming to Facebook pages, profiles, and groups.
Instagram Graph API ¹⁴	The Instagram Graph API allows the business owners to handle their Instagram business account. Using this API, business owners can read comments, get user's insights for their pages, understand business metrics, etc.

¹⁶ <https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/twitter-api/v1>

¹⁷ <https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/twitter-api/premium>

¹⁸ <https://developers.facebook.com/docs/graph-api/>

Facebook Marketing API¹⁵	This API allows business owner to execute custom marketing campaigns on Facebook advertising platform.
Facebook Pages API¹⁶	Facebook Pages API allows Facebook page owners to manage their pages programmatically. The API allows page owners to post messages on their pages, manage posts activities, etc.
Facebook Graph API¹⁷	Graph API is the most widely, commonly used and oldest API of Facebook. Every single API integrates with Facebook and make use of Graph API to read and write post data from complete Facebook platform.

- Facebook Graph API

The Facebook Graph API is the primary way to read data out from the Facebook platform and to write posts data on it. It's an HTTP-based API, in which after defining the relevant keywords one can query Facebook posts and retrieve them. The graph API has implementations available in major programming languages like python, java, JavaScript, PHP, etc. Figure 6 shows the Facebook graph API's flow independent of any programming language.

Figure 6 Facebook Graph API Flow¹⁹

- Basics of Facebook Graph API

The API works in form of a social graph. Like graph ins general, it has nodes & edges. There is additional element in this social graph called as “field”.

Nodes – This represents different individual Facebook users. Programmatically, they are individual objects with unique ID having edges as a link to other users (i-e; nodes).

Edges – This represents the relationship between one or more than one node.

Field – This represents different data about each individual nodes, like name, no. of posts, no. of friends, etc.

¹⁹ <http://s2ptech.blogspot.com/2015/05/facebook-login-with-oauth.html>

4 Techniques and methods for analysing the social media data

The fast-growing use of social media platforms and their relevant application areas have made major advancements in different ways which people use to interact with each other [17]. The in-depth analysis of social media data is sometimes difficult because of its unpredictable nature due to several facts like the data is dynamic, wide-ranging, and scattered. The recent advances in computational techniques/methods like artificial intelligence (AI) have made the in-depth analysis of social media data quite easier. These techniques help in understanding several patterns on social media platforms like social media usage, online behaviours, data/content sharing, perceptions of different types of people about certain topics, etc [18]. The extraction of these patterns can give a variety of benefits to organizations, governments, and non-profit organizations to design their services and policies focusing on user-centric methodology [19]. There have been a lot of attempts in literature for extracting valuable insights from vast social media data for better decision making. Some of the examples of such insights are analysing opinions of users towards different products, analysing election results, and understanding users' behaviours. This section will further discuss different types of AI techniques being used for analysing social media data.

4.1 Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques and methods for analysing social media data

AI techniques/methods are all about “making machines intelligent” by using variety of approaches. The field of AI has been around almost more than six decades, and it has faced many ups and downs throughout this period. In the starting days, when AI research showed a lot of promises to the communities, but those promises were somehow not fulfilled due to unavailability of digital data and computational power. This was the period of late 1980s and early 1990s and termed as “AI Winter”, where no much progress was done in terms of solving real-world problems using AI. But, later on when new techniques started to be introduced along with availability of digital data and huge computational powers AI started to increase again. Here digital data is mainly referred to online web and social media platforms data. The different AI techniques/methods for analyzing social media data both (structured and unstructured – discussed in Section 0) can be divided into three major types based on use case and ultimate goal to be achieved. Figure 7 shows the three different types of AI techniques/methods for analyzing social media data in order to understand users behaviours, patterns, communications and perceptions.

Figure 7 Types of AI Techniques

4.1.1 Machine Learning (ML)

Machine learning (ML) is a type of AI technique, used to automate solutions for complex problems that are very difficult to solve using general hand-crafted rules-based approach. The hand-crafted rules-based approach in AI was tried quite a lot in the 1980s for solving complex real-world problems but due to its impractical nature it failed [20]. The approach was consisted of two steps. 1) specification of the approach: this defined what the program is supposed to do along with steps/rules for doing it and 2) implementation of this specification using a computer programming language. Generally, this approach faced a lot of challenges when it comes to solve/automate real-world problems where specifications/rules/steps can be hard to define. One such example is “detection of handwritten characters in an image” where new characters need to be identified from an image automatically. ML solve these complex problems in a generic way [21]. This technique does not require any explicit rules/steps to design the solution, instead it learns different set of rules/steps from the set of provided data relevant to the real-world problem needs to be solved. For example, in case of handwritten character recognition from images; the data can be collection of several images with variety of numerical characters written by different set of people. In other words, this technique learns patterns, relations from the data and larger the data, the more ML learns better [22-24]. Because ML considers all the data provided for learning the rules, it becomes more accurate as compared to hand-crafted rules because there is no human-bias involve while defining the rules.

As ML is a kind of automatic learning from the data to solve any problem, this learning is divided into four different methods. These learning methods give ability to ML to learn from the available data. The data is generally of two types [25]:

- **Labelled Data:** The data available with its relevant answers/labels. For example: collection of raw images of dogs and cats along with answers that which images are of dog and cats, respectively.
- **Unlabelled Data:** The data available without the relevant answers/labels. For example: collection of raw images of dogs and cats but without any division into labels.

It is also worth to discuss here the concept of training, validation and test data before going to further discuss learning methods.

- **Training Data:** The data used to train any ML model so that it can learn the patterns and behaviours from the data.
- **Validation Data:** The data used during the training process to assess the performance of the ML model during each training step.
- **Test Data:** The new unseen data used to measure the performance of final trained ML model to evaluate its learning/understanding.

Figure 8 shows the detailed taxonomy of ML and its learning methods. The taxonomy is further discussed below.

Figure 8 Taxonomy of ML

1) Supervised Learning

In supervised learning method, the ML model is given a collection of data specific to any real-world problem along with answers/labels (i.e. labelled data). The provided data is in the form of mapping from $Input(x) \rightarrow Output(y)$, where x represents the list of data points and y represents the corresponding answers/labels. The ML model has to learn different relationships/rules of data points to their corresponding labels. When there is a new unseen data point the supervised ML model should be able to identify the label of new data point automatically [26, 27]. For example: a dataset/collection of emails with provided labels as spam or non-spam is a type of labelled data and the learned ML model to identify any new email as spam or non-spam is a type of supervised learning method. Furthermore, the supervised learning methods are divided into two types:

i. Classification [28]

When the data is labelled into two or more than two distinct non-continuous categories/labels. (i.e. emails data labelled into two labels. Spam or non-spam). The most widely used classification ML models are SVM [29], Naïve Bayes (NB) [30], Decision Tree (DT) [31], Random Forest (RF) [32], KNN, AdaBoost, etc [33].

ii. Regression [34]

When the data is labelled into continuous numbers and the ML model needs to label new data point into any continuous number. (i.e. data for different houses of different areas labelled into continuous numeric price labels). The most widely used regression ML models are Linear Regression [35] and Logistic Regression [36].

2) Unsupervised Learning

In unsupervised learning method, the ML model is given a collection of data specific to any real-world problem without any answers/labels (i.e. unlabelled data). The provided data is in the form of $Input(x)$ only, where x represents the list of data points without any labels. The ML model has to identify and differentiate different data points and combine into different groups based on its learning data. When there is a new unseen data point, the unsupervised ML models tries to put it in the most similar group learned from the previous data [37]. For example: a dataset/collection of buying patterns from several customers. The unsupervised model learns to group the customers based on buying patterns. This unsupervised learning has a very common type defined below:

a) Clustering [38]

This type refers to grouping the elements which are near to each other. The main assumption that is followed while performing grouping is that data points having similar properties should be grouped together. The most common ML model of clustering is K-means [39].

3) *Semi-Supervised Learning*

The semi-supervised learning model is a combination of both supervised and unsupervised learning. As supervised learning requires a lot of labelled data and this labelling requires a lot of time and human effort. Therefore, the semi-supervised learning model learns from the small amount of labelled data in supervised manner and then uses the unsupervised learning to label rest of the remaining data points. [40]

Figure 9 shows the common flow for the working of any ML models to achieve some objectives.

Figure 9 Common ML Flow

Furthermore, more detailed information regarding ML, its learning methods and models is also discussed in [41]. Because one of the scopes of this deliverable is to find the available methods for analysing social media data, Table 3 summarizes the state-of-the-art of different ML methods/models used for analysing social media data.

Table 3: State-of-the-art of ML models for analysing social media data

Title	ML Model Used	Dataset Used	Social Media Platform Used	Application Area
Behavioral analysis of pornographic content in social media [42]	RF	Twitter	Twitter	Behavior analysis

Predicting the churn rate of a customer [43]	RF, Naive Bayes, DT, LR, SVM	UCI ML Repository Churn dataset	-	Behavior analysis
Crowdsourcing and collaborative learning environments based on SM [44]	Gaussian Naïve Bayes	Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn	Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn	Business Intelligence
Data analytic learning with strategic decision making	DT	Twitter hashtag, Memetracker, and Yelp	Twitter	Business Intelligence
Fake profile detection	MRF	Facebook	Facebook	Crime detection
Cyberbullying Detection based on Semantic-Enhanced Marginalized Denoising Auto-Encoder.	Bow, SVM, LDA, Semantic-Enhanced Marginalized Denoising Auto-Encoder (smSDA)	Twitter, Myspace	Twitter, Myspace	Crime detection
Compromised accounts	SVM	Twitter, Facebook	Twitter, Facebook	Crime detection
Spam detection	LDA	Youtube comments	Youtube	Crime detection
Cyberstalking	CNN	Twitter	Twitter	Crime detection
Cyberbullying	SVM, ANN	Twitter	Twitter	Crime detection
Identifying Epidemics	SVM, NB, and RF	Weibo		Epidemics
detection of influenza epidemics	Linear Regression, Multiple Regression	Twitter	Twitter	Epidemics
detection of flu epidemics	SVM, NB, and RF	Twitter and IDSC	Twitter and IDSC	Epidemics
Disaster management using SM	GIS model	Satellite images		Event detection
Realtime traffic reporting	Linguistic Dynamic system and fuzzy	Twitter	Twitter	Event detection
Realtime traffic reporting by analyzing Italian language tweets.	SVM	Twitter	Twitter	Event detection

Real time crisis mapping of natural disasters using social media.	TRIDEC project	Twitter, Google Earth	Twitter	Image analysis
Generating person-specific representations used to boost face recognition performance	SVM, LDA	PubFig83		Image analysis
Deep Aging Face Verification with Large Gaps	Deep aging face verification (DAFV) framework, CNN	Cross-age face (CAFE)		Image analysis
Improving information diffusion in SM	Independent cascade (IC) model and the linear threshold (LT) model	Douban, AMiner, DBLP, and LiveJournal		Recommenders systems
Data analytic learning with strategic decision making	Chinese Restaurant-Game framework	Twitter hashtag, Memetracker, and Yelp		Recommenders systems
Constructing recommender systems using Collaborative Filtering by Trust	SVM, Matrix Factorization	Epinions, Douban and Flixster		Recommenders systems

4) Performance metrics for Learning Methods

- Confusion Matrix

In classification problems, the confusion matrix is one of the most used metrics to measure the overall performance of the trained models. Almost all performance metrics i.e. accuracy, precision, recall, etc. use the terms or numbers that are present inside the confusion matrix [45]. Terms used in Confusion Matrix as following:

- **True Positive (TP):** It represents the cases when the actual class of data point is true and trained model also predict it as true.
- **True Negative (TN):** These are the cases when the actual class of data point is false and trained model also predict it as false.
- **False Positive (FP):** False positive refers to the cases when the actual class of data point is false but the trained model predicts it as true.
- **False Negative (FN):** False negative shows the cases where the actual class of instance was true but the trained model incorrectly classifies it as false.

- Accuracy

The accuracy refers to the number of correctly predicted instances (true positives and true negatives) by the trained model over the total number of instances. Formally:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN}$$

- Precision

Precision is also known as positive predicted values. This is the proportion of predicted positive instances that would also be true in real. Formally:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

- Recall or Sensitivity

Recall is the proportion of instances that are actually positive would also be predicted by the algorithm as positive. Formally:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

- Specificity

This is opposite to recall. Specificity is a proportion of instances that are negative, were also predicted by the model as negative. Formally:

$$Specificity = \frac{TN}{TN + FP}$$

- F1-Measure Score

This is the combination of precision and recall. Formally:

$$F - \text{measure} = \frac{2 \times (\text{precision} \times \text{recall})}{(\text{precision} + \text{recall})}$$

4.1.2 Deep Learning (DL)

Deep learning is a sub-type of ML which mimics the same way which humans use to gain or understand certain types of information and knowledge. The major different between ML and DL is the composition of its models where ML models are linear in nature and DL models are stacked hierarchical and complex in nature [46]. Another advantage of using deep learning is the automatic learning of important features from the raw data contributing towards decision making. The machine learning, we discussed previously is more often dependent on human intervention to learn. Deep learning is also referred as “Deep Neural Networks (DNNs)”. The simple neural networks, also referred as “Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)” are structured and motivated by human brain reflecting the same way the biological neurons work [47]. The ANNs are consisted of hierarchical node layers containing an input later, one or more than one hidden layer and an output layer. The DNNs are the special kind of ANNs with more than one hidden layer. Figure 10 shows the basic architecture of a simple DNN.

Figure 10 Basic Architecture of a Simple DNN ²⁰

Like ML, there are several types of DNNs based on the objective/problem that needs to be achieved/solved using deep learning. Figure 11 shows the detailed taxonomy of DL/DNNs and is further discussed below.

Figure 11 Taxonomy of DL

²⁰ <https://www.ibm.com/cloud/learn/neural-networks#toc-what-are-n-2oQ5Vepe>

1. Deep Supervised Learning

The DNNs for supervised learning [48] works in the same way and purpose as in the supervised learning in ML. These DNNs need the labelled data to learn the relationship and extract patterns for mapping of the input data to its corresponding output labels. These DNNs are further divided into same two types, classification, and regression. Same as defined in ML. The popular algorithms/models for DNNs for supervised learning are Dense Networks (DenseNets) [49], Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [50], Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) [51], Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) Networks [52], Bi-LSTM Networks[53] etc.

2. Deep Unsupervised Learning

The DNNs for unsupervised learning [54] refers to the learning where there is no labelled data. In other words, it works with the unlabelled data in the same logic as unsupervised learning in ML. The most common types of these DNNs are AutoEncoders [55] and Deep Boltzmann Machines [56].

3. Deep Semi-Supervised Learning

The DNNs have already demonstrated their performance on variety of deep supervised and unsupervised learning (i.e. image classification [57]) once trained on extensively large labelled dataset (i.e. ImageNet [58]). However, this creates a bottleneck of creating large datasets while working with DNNs which requires extensive amount time, resources, and effort. To avoid this bottleneck, recently the DNNs for semi supervised learning [59] are introduced. The most common types of these algorithms/models are Active Learning [60] and Weakly-Supervised Learning [61].

Table 4: State-of-the-art of DL models for analysing social media data

Title	DL Model Used	Dataset Used	Social Media Platform Used	Year	Application Area
Age Groups Classification in Social Network Using Deep Learning [62]	MLP, DCNN, DT, RF, SVM	Medical domain related tweets	Twitter	2017	Behaviour Analysis
Deep Learning Model for Integration of Clustering with Ranking in Social Networks [63]	Deep Learning Cluster Rank (DeepLCRank)	Holiday photo images	Flickr, YouTube	2017	Behaviour Analysis
Deep Learning for Hate Speech Detection in Tweets [64]	FastText + CNN, LSTM	Racist tweets dataset	Twitter	2017	Hate Speech
Detecting Offensive Language in Tweets Using Deep Learning [65]	RNN	Hate speech tweets	Twitter	2018	Hate Speech

Multi-layers Convolutional Neural Network for Twitter Sentiment Ordinal Scale Classification [66]	CNN	SemEval challenge dataset ²¹	Twitter	2018	Sentiment Analysis
Bloom’s Learning Outcomes’ Automatic Classification Using LSTM and Pretrained Word Embeddings [67]	FastText + LSTM	Course learning outcomes dataset	Twitter	2021	Bloom’s Taxonomy
Evaluating Polarity Trend Amidst the Coronavirus Crisis in Peoples’ Attitudes toward the Vaccination Drive [68]	FastText + LSTM	Covid-19 tweets	Twitter	2021	Sentiment Analysis
Deep learning-based personality recognition from text posts of online social networks [69]	CNN, RNN	Facebook posts	Facebook	2018	Personality Recognition
Personality recognition from Facebook text for Portuguese language [70]	LSTM	Facebook posts	Facebook	2018	Personality Recognition

4.1.3 Natural Language Processing (NLP)

The NLP field, also referred as computational linguistics, is the subfield of AI which gives an ability to the computers to process and understand the natural language (i.e. human language) in the same way as human do. The natural language is usually in the form of free text. Although, the field of NLP was introduced half a century ago but still till today it is facing a lot of challenges.

As Andras Kornai has quoted in one his book: *“It is hard from the standpoint of the child, who must spend many years acquiring a language ... it is hard for the adult language learner, it is hard for the scientist who attempts to model the relevant phenomena, and it is hard for the engineer who attempts to build systems that deal with natural language input or output. These tasks are so hard that Turing could rightly make fluent conversation in natural language the centerpiece of his test for intelligence [66].”*

The goal of the NLP field is to read, decode, understand, and extract valuable, sensible insights and information from the human language. One of the scopes of this deliverable is to explain different methods for analysing social media data. Therefore, it is worth to explore the field of NLP. Because most of the social media data is in the form of free text, it is worth exploring how NLP can be used for it. The first step when it comes to analyse unstructured text data is to convert it into the structured

²¹ <http://alt.qcri.org/semeval2016/task4/index.php%3fid%3ddata-and-tools>

form. Such that the computers can understand that data. The common pipeline for converting unstructured text data into structured data is given in Figure 12.

Figure 12 From Unstructured to Structured Data using NLP

1. Unstructured Text Data

The data which does not have any defined data model or structure such that it cannot be processed easily by the computers. The most common types of such data are: online social media data, online blogs data, news websites data, electronic documents data, etc.

2. Text Pre-processing

Most of the times the unstructured text data has a lot of noise and irrelevant information which do not contribute for valuable insights and information extraction. In NLP, we have very good techniques available that can be used to pre-process/clean the unstructured text data. The most common techniques are shown in Figure 132. The different text pre-processing techniques are shown in Figure 13 and the details for each of the technique is explained in [67, 71, 72]. Most of the programming language like python, JAVA, etc have built-in NLP libraries working with text pre-processing. The famous NLP libraries for python language are NLTK²², CoreNLP²³, Gensim²⁴, Spacy²⁵ and Pattern²⁶. Moreover, the famous NLP libraries for JAVA are OpenNLP²⁷, Stanford CoreNLP²⁸ and Freeling²⁹.

²² <https://www.nltk.org/>

²³ <https://github.com/stanfordnlp/python-stanford-corenlp>

²⁴ <https://pypi.org/project/gensim/>

²⁵ <https://spacy.io/>

²⁶ <https://analyticsindiamag.com/hands-on-guide-to-pattern-a-python-tool-for-effective-text-processing-and-data-mining/>

²⁷ <https://opennlp.apache.org/>

²⁸ <https://stanfordnlp.github.io/CoreNLP/>

²⁹ <http://nlp.lsi.upc.edu/freeling/node/1>

Figure 13 Text Pre-processing techniques in NLP

3. Text Parsing

Text parsing is a technique of NLP for understanding the unstructured text data. When it comes to understanding, it involves two types of techniques. 1) Syntactic Analysis and 2) Semantic Analysis. This section will only discuss syntactic analysis because text parsing is a syntactic analysis technique. The term “Syntactic” is derived from the word “Syntax”. Every language has its own syntax which define its grammatical structure while writing the text. The syntactic analysis/text parsing techniques are used to understand grammatical structure of the human language based on formal grammar rules and meaningfulness [73]. The computer program which performs the text parsing is called “Text Parser”. The most common types of text parsing for NLP are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Text Parsing Techniques for NLP

Text Parsing Technique	Reference
Parts of Speech (POS) Tagging	[74]
Shallow Parsing or Chunking	[75]
Constituency Parsing	[76]
Dependency Parsing	[71]

4. Feature Engineering

Feature Engineering is a technique used in NLP for understanding information from the raw text. This technique is mainly used to convert raw text into numeric form so that it can be further

processed and understood by the computers while performing any task [77]. As this is a core step while converting the text into numerics so maintaining the same meaning and scope is very important here. Each numeric feature value is the representation of words and their relationships within the raw text. Figure 14 shows an example of feature engineering for raw data.

Figure 14 Example of Feature Engineering³⁰

There are several existing techniques available for feature engineering in NLP. The techniques are divided into three broad categories and discussed below.

b) Meta Features [78]

These are the high-level features for any raw text just like the meta-data of any data. Different types of texts have different meta features information which distinguish one type of text from other. Some of the examples for meta features are: no. of words in a text, no. of unique words in a text, no. of characters in a text, average length of a text, average length of words, etc. Although, these are somehow good features to distinguish and represent different texts but still suffer from the overlapping of the feature values when there are two different texts. The computer program will consider both the texts as same with same feature values. To solve this problem, text-based features were proposed.

c) Text Based Features [79]

These are the low-level features for any raw text and represents the words relations with each other inside a text. Additionally, these features are distinct and unique for each of the word inside a text. Finally, when we combine text-based features of individual words inside a text then for two different texts there are always different feature values. The common types of text-based features are: Bag-of-words [80], Tf-Idf [81], N-grams [82], CountVectorizer [83]. The only problem with these features is they are not very good when it comes to extract meanings, semantics or contexts inside the text.

d) Semantic / Contextual Features

These are the set of features representing the meaning and context of words inside any text. These features play an important role while working with same words but in different context. For example: the word “long” has positive semantic/meaning when used with the word “battery” and has negative meaning when it is used with the words “working hours”. As compared to text-based and meta features, the semantic features help to extract this contextual meaning from the text easily. Word2Vec [84] and Doc2Vec [85] are the very first types of these features. In NLP terminology, these

³⁰ <https://towardsdatascience.com/how-to-turn-text-into-features-478b57632e99>

semantic features are often termed as “Word Embeddings” as well. The recent types of these features are FastText [86], Glove [87] and Elmo [88].

5. Structured Data

Once, the feature engineering is completed the raw text data (i.e., unstructured data) will be in form of numbers and representing the structured data.

Next, we will discuss what are the different techniques available in NLP used for analyzing social media text to extract useful insights and information. These extracted insights help to understand user perceptions related to the domain. We will also discuss how NLP is combined with ML and DL models to extract insights from social media data. Figure 15 shows the detail taxonomy of some of the important NLP techniques used for perception extraction from the social media data.

4.1.4 NLP Techniques

Figure 15 Taxonomy of NLP techniques for perception extraction

I. Sentiment Analysis Techniques

Sentiment analysis (SA) also referred as Opinion Mining (OM) is a technique to extract and analyse people’s opinions, attitudes, behaviours, perceptions, etc towards different topics, products, issues being discussed on social media platforms. It is a powerful technique for businesses, industries, governments and other entities to extract and understand users mood and views [89]. The general sentiment analysis assesses the data in form of positive, negative, or neutral. However, there is more granular type of sentiment analysis used which is “emotion analysis”. The emotion analysis tends to identify different emotions like anger, fear, sadness, surprise, joy, etc from the social media text [90]. On social media platforms, people are free to express their opinions and perceptions on wide range of topics. To perform sentiment and emotion analysis on those opinions and feedbacks help to understand the users views and perceptions [91]. In general, there are three levels of sentiment analysis.

- Sentence Level

In this level, the sentiment analysis is performed on individual sentences inside any text. In case of longer texts, the texts are separated into individual sentences [92].

- Document Level

At this level, the sentiment is performed on the whole document containing one or more than one sentences [93].

- Aspect Level

At this level, sentiment analysis is performed against specific feature, aspect or topic from the text. For example, the speed of the machine is high, but it has very high cost. Here speed and cost are the two aspects [94].

Next, we will discuss what are the different approaches available in the literature for performing sentiment analysis for social media text. Figure 14 shows the taxonomy of different techniques available for performing sentiment analysis.

Figure 16 Taxonomy of Sentiment Analysis Techniques

Lexicon-based approaches are the simple dictionary-based approaches where different words and phrases are already labelled with different sentiment scores. The overall sentiment score of a text depends on the collective scores of individual words and phrases. Christopher et al. in [95] performed comparison of six different lexicon-based approaches to perform sentiment analysis. The authors evaluated all the six approaches against manually labelled amazon reviews dataset. Although, the authors achieved good accuracy in the range of 75%-77% using Hu & Liu lexicon **but the problem with this approach is that it is very limited in the scope and only applicable for the domain of product reviews.**

To overcome the lexicon-based approach challenges, several authors used machine learning based approaches for performing sentiment analysis. To perform machine learning approach, the text data needs to be converted into the numeric data according to the steps provided in the section “Natural Language Processing (NLP)”. Ye et al. in [96] applied supervised machine learning algorithms namely, SVM, NB and N-gram model on yahoo reviews of famous travel destinations. The authors achieved overall 87% accuracy with N-gram model. The authors in [97] performed a systematic literature review for different machine learning models applied for performing sentiment analysis for online reviews data. **The main limitation with supervised machine learning model is the available of already labelled training data into sentiment labels. Another limitation of using machine learning is the manual/hand crafted feature engineering for text data.**

To solve the manual feature engineering problem recently many researchers have applied the deep learning approaches to perform sentiment analysis in social media text. The deep learning algorithms automatically identifies and extract important features from the text. Pasupa et al. in [98] performed sentiment analysis using three deep learning models; CNN, LSTM and BiLSTM. The authors observed overall accuracy of 81% using CNN deep learning model. **The major limitation with using deep learning approaches is again the need of large labelled training dataset for performing sentiment analysis in specific domains.**

Table 6 shows the SoTA studies for sentiment analysis applied in various domains.

Table 6 State-of-the-art sentiment analysis techniques

Reference	Level	Technique	Feature extraction	Learning algorithm	Domain	Results
Songbo et al. [99]	Sentence level	Machine learning	–	NB, SVM, KNN	House Movie Education	SVM F1-Score: 90%
Moraes et al. [100]	Aspect level	Machine learning Deep learning	Bag of words	NB, SVM ANN	Movies Books GPS	ANN Movies Dataset → 86.5% accuracy Books Dataset → 90.6% accuracy GPS Dataset → 81.8% accuracy
Tang et al. [101]	Document level	Deep learning	Word embeddings	CNN	Movies	CNN Accuracy: 60.8%
Dahou et al. [102]	–	Deep learning	Word embeddings	CNN	Books Movies Restaurants	CNN Accuracy: 91.7%
Ahuja et al. [103]	Sentence level	Machine learning	TF-IDF n-gram	KNN, SVM, LR, NB, RF	–	LR Accuracy: 57%
Untawale et al. [104]	–	Machine learning	–	NB, RF	Movies	NB
Shamantha et al. [105]	-	Machine learning	–	NB, SVM, RF	Twitter	NB Accuracy: 80%
Goularas et al. [106]	–	Machine learning	–	RF, SVM	–	RF Accuracy: 95%
Nandal et al. [107]	Aspect level	Machine learning	–	SVM	–	SVM
Sharma et al. [108]	–	Machine learning Deep learning	–	SVM DNN	Twitter	DNN Accuracy: 87.5%

Figure 18 Topic Modelling Approaches

c. Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA)

This technique was proposed by Landauer and Dumais in 1997, and is the first technique to be used for performing topic modelling [111]. The main concept of LSA is based on the concept of Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) [112, 113], which states that the words/topics with the similar meaning also occur very close to each other in terms of the context. All the similarity calculation is directly calculated from the text itself by performing the feature engineering on the raw text. Finally, this technique uses clustering to make groups of topics having similar meaning. LSA has been actively used for information retrieval, social network analysis and text summarization[[]].

d. Non-Negative Matrix Factorization

This is an unsupervised technique such that there is no already labelled topics on which model will be trained. This technique decomposes (or factorizes) high-dimensional vectors into a lower-dimensional vectors representation. This concept was introduced by Pattero et al. in 1994 for environmental data [114]. The Lee et al. used this technique for performing topic modelling in unsupervised way [115].

e. Probabilistic Latent Semantic Analysis

This technique works same as LSA as defined above but instead of using SVD method, it uses the probabilistic method to generate the topics [116].

f. Latent Dirichlet Allocation

This topic modelling technique is based on defineti theorem [117]. This technique makes an assumption that each of the text contains several texts topics with different proportions. Those topics are actually part of a big corpus. So, this technique aims to learn these topics from the text. It is purely based on bag of words (BOW) approach. This technique uses generative process as a combine probability distribution over both observed and hidden variables.

Although, the traditional approaches show very promising results and were used in variety of studies for performing topic modelling on social media data [118-121]. However, these approaches suffer from variety of limitations such as:

- Limit in the number of topics to be detected
- Generate generic topics

- There is trouble in dealing with topics that have complex generalization-specialization relationships.
- Less relevance of the generated topics to topics in the real-world
- Do not capture topic-inherent properties

To overcome above shortcomings, recently new techniques for topic modelling in social media data analysis are evolved based on the advancements of machine and deep learning models. These kinds of approaches are classified into two types: 1) supervised topic modelling, 2) unsupervised topic modelling [122]. Table 7 shows the SoTA studies for topic modelling applied in various domains.

Table 7 Recent Topic Modelling Approaches

Reference	Type	Feature extraction	Learning algorithm	Domain	Year
Gencoglu et al. [123]	Unsupervised	Contextual Word Embedding	K-Means	Health	2018
Ma et al. [124]	Supervised	Contextual Word Embedding	BERT	Disaster Management	2018
Hu et al. [125]	Supervised	Pre-trained Word Embedding	CNN, SVM	Sentiment Analysis	2018
Hasan et al. [126]	Unsupervised	Word Embedding	Incremental Clustering	Twitter News	2019
Tembhurnikar et al. [127]	Unsupervised	n-grams	K-means	Twitter	2015

III. Subjectivity Analysis

Subjectivity analysis categorizes any text between two categories: 1) subjective, 2) objective. Usually, whenever any content is shared on social media it belongs to one of the above categories or sometimes it belongs to both categories. If a text contains only facts or general information about any topic or event it is categorized as objective text. On the other hand, if a text contains any opinion, sentiment, or subjective expression then it is categorized as subjective text. Subjectivity analysis also helps different organizations, product owners, technology providers, etc to understand how people are reacting towards their products, technologies, etc [128]. Table summarizes the state-of-the-art of subjectivity analysis approaches

Table 8: state-of-the-art of subjectivity analysis approaches

Reference	Type	Feature extraction	Learning algorithm	Domain	Year
Kumat et al. [129]	Dictionary, Corpus Based	WordNet, POS	-	General	2012
Ortega et al. [130]	Unsupervised Learning	WordNet, SentiWordNet	-	Telecommunication	2013

IV. Intent Detection

Intent detection is one of the new areas in NLP and is related to the field of Natural Language Understanding (NLU). Intention detection is all about extracting intentions of the users from the text to understand what the user wants to say [131]. For example: in banking domain, the users always try to put queries related to card arrival, card linking, exchange rate, pending cash withdrawal, etc. All these purposes communicated by the users serve as the intent of the query. The automatic detection of the intents can improve the customer service department by automatically forwarding queries related to specific intent to the relevant department [132]. Previously, intent detection was only used for the chatbots for understanding user queries but now it is also used in other domains like airline and travel information systems[133], banking [132] and medical [134]. Table 9 shows some of the SoTA intent detection approaches for various domains.

Table 9 state-of-the-art of intent detection approaches

Reference	Approach	Dataset	Feature extraction	Learning algorithm	Domain	Results	Year
Cohan et al. [135]	Supervised	SciCite dataset, ACL-ARC citations dataset	ELMo	BiLSTM	Scientific Publications	84% accuracy	2019
Adekotujo et al. [136]	Supervised	Crisis events tweets	Bi-gram + crossEntropy	NB, SVM	Twitter	N/A	2018
Chen et al. [137]	Supervised	ATIS dataset	BERT embeddings	BERT	Airline information system	98.6% accuracy	2019
Huang et al. [138]	Supervised	Github issue reports	embeddings	CNN	Github	86% accuracy	2018
Abbet et al. [139]	Supervised	Churn customers dataset	Bilingual word embeddings	CNN	Twitter	84% accuracy	2018

V. Keyword/Keyphrase Extraction

Keyword/Keyphrase extraction is a NLP technique for extracting important words/concepts, relevant to the underlying document/text [140]. This technique helps in several ways like grouping of texts based on similar keywords, important concepts/topics being discussed in the texts,

document searching and filtering based on extracted keywords, etc [141]. Generally, this extraction is a two-way process: 1) to generate candidate words from the text, 2) to select and rank the candidate words based on their impact on the text [142]. Figure 17 shows the common SOTA approaches for this technique.

Figure 19 Keyword/Keyphrase Extraction SOTA Approaches

a. Statistical Approach

This approach does not require any prior training for keyword/keyphrase extraction from the text. This approach generates the candidate keywords based on statistics from the text like word frequency, probability, other feature engineering techniques [143] like TFIDF [144], N-gram [145] and common word occurrences [146]. One of the popular algorithm using this approach is YAKE [147].

b. ML + DL Approach

In this approach, generally a ML/DL classifier is trained on a labelled keyword/keyphrase documents where a extracted keyword is labelled as relevant keyword or not. It is a binary classification task. One of the traditional keyword extraction system based on this approach is “KEA [148]”, which uses TFIDF scores along with NB classifier to predict whether a candidate sentence is a keyword/keyphrase or not. Furthermore, McIlraith and Weinberger in [149] proposed “SurfKE” which is also a keyword/keyphrase extraction technique based on this approach using NB classifier.

c. Graph Based Approach

This approach generates a graph of keywords/keyphrases related to each other from the text/document. The graph connects co-occurring terms in the text with each other. This approach uses graph ranking methods and set the score in terms of vertex importance to show the importance of the terms associated with the specific vertex. The famous algorithms using this approach are TextRank [150] and RAKE [151].

d. Hybrid Approach

This approach generates the candidate keywords/keyphrases based on combination of one or more approaches from the above. For example:

- ExpandRank [152]: combination of TFIDF + graph-based approach
- PositionRank [153] : combination of word occurrences with graph-based approach

Table 10 shows some of the SoTA studies for keyword/keyphrase extraction for various domains.

Table 10 state-of-the-art of keyword/keyphrase extraction approaches

Reference	Approach	Dataset	Learning algorithm	Domain	Results	Year
Alzaidy et al. [154]	Unsupervised	Research articles	BiLSTM CRF	Scientific documents	42% accuracy	2019
Wang et al. [155]	Unsupervised	Research articles	BiLSTM	Scientific documents	29% accuracy	2018
Basaldella et al. [156]	Unsupervised	INSPECT dataset	BiLSTM	Scientific documents	42% accuracy	2018
Ye and Wang et al. [157]	Semi-supervised	INSPEC, Krapivin, SEmEval	Seq2Seq	multiple	INSPEC: 33% accuracy, Krapivin: 29% accuracy, SemEval: 29% accuracy	2018
Florescu et al. [158]	Graph based	News articles	--	News	26% accuracy	2018

5 Perception Extraction from Social Media Data

User perceptions about any events, topics, policies, etc. have always appealed the attention of policy and decision makers. These perceptions are always considered as strong evidence for making and adjusting user-centric decisions [159-161]. The traditional method of analyzing/investigating user perceptions is usually based on data collection from survey polls and questionnaires. Next, the collected data is analyzed using traditional qualitative and quantitative methods [162, 163]. However, some of the researchers have argued that these kinds of approaches more likely represent small group of individual user perceptions rather than public user perceptions [164, 165]. Furthermore, due to the time and costs constraints involved in survey and questionnaire activities, the amount of collected data is very limited and hence it restricts the overall findings for understanding user perceptions to a large extent [166].

Now a days, social media platforms like Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, etc. offer a new way of understanding and measuring user perceptions. There has been an increase in adopting and using social media platforms by the general public as well as the enterprises, industry owners, government officials, scientists, scholars, etc. [167]. The understanding and extraction of user perceptions from social media data has been widely studied in several domains including social science [168], education [169], politics [170], marketing [171], healthcare [172], finance [173] and disaster management [174]. Hence, using social media data as a data source for user perception extraction and analysis can overcome the limitations of traditional surveys and questionnaires methods [175]. Salleh et al. concluded that the perception extraction from social media data shows the understanding of public perceptions in a more scientific manner. Also, it is helpful in forecasting future user perceptions related to any event, topic or policies which ultimately helps in shaping overall society's viewpoint [176].

As discussed in section 4.1.3, most of the times the social media data is in form of unstructured text and to understand or extract perceptions one needs to process it. We have already discussed the

various machine learning, deep learning and NLP techniques for processing the unstructured social media data in above sections 4.1.1, 4.1.2, 4.1.3, and 4.1.4. Xuefan et al. in [177] conducted review on perception extraction and understanding on social media data. According to the review results, Twitter is the most widely used social media platform for perceptions extraction along with Facebook and other platforms. The most frequent keywords of the studies included in the review are social media, twitter, sentiment analysis, public perception, public engagement, opinion mining, NLP, and perceptions. The major techniques used for perception extraction from the studies included in the review are sentiment analysis and topic modelling. Although, there are strong state-of-the-art studies available for perception extraction from social media data in different domains as shown in the section 4. Particularly, there is a lack of studies focusing on user perception extraction for SBC technologies. The upcoming sections will specifically focus on perception extraction for SBC technologies as per scope of the T6.2 from WP6 in METICOS.

6 Existing application areas for perception extraction from social media data

Social media data analysis is being applied many application areas, like health, tourism, business, supply chain. Some of the major application areas of social media data analysis along with relevant social media platform are listed in Table 11. Some of the few recent studies are discussed below in which social media analysis is used.

Table 11 Perception extraction from social media application areas

Title	Year	Domain	Social Media Platform
Social media data analysis to predict mental state of users using machine learning techniques [178]	2021	Health	Twitter
The application of artificial intelligence and data integration in COVID-19 studies: a scoping review [179]	2021	Health, COVID-19	Twitter
Exploring temporal suicidal behaviour patterns on social media: Insight from Twitter analytics [180]	2020	Health	Twitter
Social media insights into US mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic: longitudinal analysis of twitter data [181]	2020	Health	Twitter
Analyzing social media, analyzing the social? A methodological discussion about the demoscopic and predictive potential of social media [182]	2020	Politics	Twitter
A case study in belief surveillance, sentiment analysis, and identification of informational targets for e-cigarettes interventions [183]	2019	Health	Twitter
Realizing social-media-based analytics for smart agriculture [184]	2019	Agriculture	Twitter
Social media analytics: Extracting and visualizing Hilton hotel ratings and reviews from TripAdvisor [185]	2019	Tourism	TripAdvisor
Leveraging social media to gain insights into service delivery: a study on Airbnb [186]	2019	Tourism	AirBnB Reviews
Using Classification Technique for Customer Relationship Management based on Thai Social Media Data [187]	2019	Business	Facebook
A new approach of social media analytics to predict service quality: evidence from the airline industry [188]	2019	Business	Twitter
Topic modeling and sentiment analysis of global climate change tweets [189]	2019	Climate Change	Twitter
Identifying racist social media comments in Sinhala language using text analytics models with machine learning [190]	2018	Social Issues	Facebook

The Twitter Bullishness Index: A Social Media Analytics Indicator for the Stock Market [191]	2016	Stock Market	Twitter
Analyzing Twitter to explore perceptions of Asian restaurants [192]	2016	Tourism	Twitter

From the Table 11, we can conclude that perception extraction from social media data is still not used in the border control technologies' domain

7 METICOS and Border Control Technologies on social media platforms

The METICOS dissemination and communication team has chosen to utilise social media accounts on Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Zenodo. Using content that matches each platform's structural affordances and features SEO characteristics (e.g., relevant hashtags) combined with the partners' already existing accounts, METICOS accounts are going to be used to increase project visibility in social networking sites. Four social media channels are currently used: Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and Zenodo.

The information and statistics of METICOS's social media accounts can be found below:

Table 12 METICOS social media accounts information

Social media platform	URL	Statistics	Date
Website	https://meticos-project.eu/	Views:6.1K, Events:16K	11/2020
Twitter	https://twitter.com/MeticosEU	Tweets Impressions:26.402, Profile visits:6.043, Mentions:37, Followers:182	10/2020
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/meticos.eu/	Follows:467, Reach:6.500	11/2020
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/meticos-eu/	Followers:212, Impressions:5.917	11/2020
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/communities/meticos_eu_project/about/	0 - A simple platform- repository with no content yet	01/2021

8 Perception extraction about the METICOS and Border Control Technologies

As perception extraction from the social media data is one of the key components of the WP6 and METICOS to understand the travellers' as well as border staffs' perceptions during their interaction with the border control technologies. However, the section 5 highlights one of the key problems that although perception extraction from social media data has been used for various domains like e-

learning, e-commerce, covid-19, business, healthcare, etc but it is still not explored for border control technologies domain.

Therefore, based on SoTA understanding and acquired knowledge we have designed a perception extraction architecture pipeline for performing perception extraction from social media data in context of border control technologies. Figure 20 shows the pipeline architecture for perception extraction from social media data for border control technologies.

Figure 20 Perception extraction pipeline for border control technologies

Figure 21 shows the selection of technologies/algorithms for implementing each of the component involved in the perception extraction architecture pipeline for border control technologies. This is the preliminary selection based on SoTA mentioned in the above sections. For each of the components, we have mentioned the existing challenges specifically for border control technologies along with our preliminary selected technologies/algorithms to solve those challenges. The detailed implementation details of the proposed solutions along with complete flow is discussed below in section 9.3.

Subjectivity Classification	Intent Classification	Sentiment Analysis	Keyword/Keyphrase Extraction	Aspect Classification
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training SOTA models on 1 benchmark dataset • Proposed Technique: best ML/DL model will be selected to classify subjectivity for SBC technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No existing work for SBC technologies • Defined our own set of intents (slide:23) • Proposed Technique: Zero-shot learning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of already sentiment labelled training dataset for SBC tweets • Proposed Technique: Automatic sentiment label generation technique with fine-tuned transformer model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No existing benchmark dataset available • Proposed technique: graph-based hierarchal method using unsupervised method - KeyBERT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No existing work for SBC technologies • Defined our own set of technology aspects (slide:23) • Proposed Technique: Zero-shot learning

Figure 21 Technological details for perception extraction components

9 Preliminary Results

This section discusses the results from keywords analysis for border control technologies, data collection from Twitter and experimental results from the perception extraction pipeline defined in section 9.

9.1 Keywords Analysis

To start with data collection from the online social media platforms for border control technologies we defined a set of keywords based on METICOS proposal and D6.1 results. Some of the keywords are **“automated border control, border control technology, BorderXpress, e-gates, entry/exit system, ETIAS, Meticos”** as shown in Figure 22 on left most side. To validate the scope of those keywords, we analysed their popularity using the google trends. The process to search and analyse keywords search on google trends platform is already explained on p.15. We analysed the popularity of the keywords worldwide based on past five years. Figure 22 shows the sum of search counts for the selected keywords based on their popularity on google web search. The figure supports the selection of the keywords as all the keywords have been very popular in past five years. The most popular keyword is “entry/exit system”. Also, the maximum search for the keywords related to border control technologies were made in the year 2019 as shown in Figure 23. For the first step, the choice of the keywords is based on the METICOS proposal and D6.1 results, but for the next step we will be planning to work on defining keywords using a systematic strategy based on assessment of related keywords and their correlating terms. The next section will discuss the process of data collection based on the selected keywords.

9.1.1 Possible bias in keyword analysis

This section shows the possible bias/discrimination that can occur while selecting keywords for performing the data collection from online social media sources. Along with identification of bias, this section also explains the ways we followed to avoid the bias.

1) The choice of keywords in keyword-based queries

The choice of keywords for collecting data from social media data is a very crucial step because this step ultimately affects overall the data which we collect. The bias involved at this step will ultimately create challenges for the next steps such as data collection (amount of data), building predictive models and obtaining predictions with the built models. The major bias that may occur in the choice of keywords is related to the use of synonyms (same keywords) in different domains which ultimately leads to having incorrect or in appropriate data for the specific domain we focus on as per our requirement [193]. That is, it may be difficult to identify which domain a keyword is representing in a particular tweet and hence the keyword maybe assigned to an unintended domain in reverse to what the tweet intends. Same goes for the use of hashtags in the twitter content. That is, correlation between a hashtag and a domain maybe set incorrectly. Another bias that may occur in the choice of keywords is when only keywords/hashtags explicitly defined for the tweet and not from the tweet content are considered. Also, not having enough number of keywords to choose from is an additional bias which leads to collection of less amount of data.

Solution → To deal with the above bias in the choice of keywords, we applied several below strategies.

- i) We used google trends to expand our list of keywords for queries. We searched for “e-gates” in the google trends and it gives additional relevant keywords representing the border control technologies domain.
- ii) We use keyword search in the twitter API not only on explicitly defined keywords for the tweets but also in the tweet content.
- iii) As per the case of using same keywords for different domains, this bias is automatically resolved because our domain is quite distinct in terms of context.

Yearwise Keywords Analysis (Google Trends)

Keyword	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	Grand Total
automated border control	0	553	656	629	355	163	2,356
border control technology	98	478	461	590	529	327	2,483
BorderXpress	0	100	182	82	77	324	765
e-gates	116	452	314	728	258	351	2,219
entry/exit system	47	756	750	941	615	966	4,275
ETIAS	88	247	595	1,142	1,029	1,029	4,130
meticos	149	664	523	328	369	236	2,269
Grand Total	498	3,250	3,481	4,440	3,432	3,396	18,497

Figure 22 Border control technologies keywords' trends on google web search

Figure 23 Border control technologies keywords' popularity for past 05 years

9.2 Data Collection

Once the keywords are selected and analysed in the previous section, we started the data collection process from the social media platforms. While the data collection process is an integral part of WP7 and more specifically T7.1, in this section we are describing the process followed for the collection of the data necessary to provide extracted perceptions needed in WP6. To start with first set of data collection, we selected the Twitter social media platform because it provides an easiest access to its data collection API as compared to other social media platforms. We applied and received access for “Twitter Academic Search API” to collect the tweets. This API gives ability to collect maximum of 10 million tweets in total in a month. The type of data we receive from this API is a personal data that must still be anonymized as the API does not proceed to anonymisation. The steps performed for anonymizing the collected data are discussed in the section 9.2.1. We implemented this API using a pre-built package in python programming language and provided our relevant inputs to the API shown in Table 13. The type of information retrieved from the API against each tweet is given in Table 14. Finally, we retrieved 0.17 million tweets in total. Figure 24 shows the sample of collected data in form of excel files. Figure 25 shows count of each of the keyword involved in collection tweets for border control technologies. Figure 26 shows the count of tweets based on years involved in collecting tweets for border control technologies from 2011 to 2021.

Table 13 Input provided to Twitter Academic Search API

Input Provided	Value
Search Keyword	List of keywords defined in section 9.1
From Date	2011-01-01
To Date	2021-09-16

Table 14 Meta data retrieved from Twitter API for each tweet

Information Retrieved from Twitter													
tweet_id	language	tweet_text	source	created_at	retweet_count	reply_count	like_count	quote_count	user_location	user_verified	user_created_at	user_tweet_count	
1	en	Impressionsday 14, via Twitter for Android	Twitter for Android	2017-12-29T20:58:47.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2009-02-14T01:31:45.000Z	251279	
2	en	Impressionsday 14 M, via Twitter for Android	Twitter for Android	2017-12-29T20:58:52.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2009-02-14T01:31:45.000Z	251279	
3	en	Impressions gets it!	Twitter for Android	2017-12-29T07:52:42.000Z	0	0	0	0	Switzerland	False	2017-12-27T20:04:40.000Z	57	
4	en	@heatherowenp	Twitter for Android	2017-12-28T22:38:47.000Z	0	1	0	0	Schönbühl, Switzerland	False	2015-03-10T21:21:13.000Z	1237	
5	en	@heatherowenp	Twitter for Android	2017-12-28T19:17:46.000Z	0	1	0	0	Oxford	False	2009-10-04T10:08:09.000Z	838	
6	en	Ok @heatherowenp see you!	Twitter for Android	2017-12-28T17:25:25.000Z	0	0	1	0	Münster	False	2013-02-18T00:40:12.000Z	555	
7	en	Even more bitter with Twitter for iPhone	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-27T21:14:06.000Z	0	0	0	0	ON/A	False	2010-11-02T14:41:47.000Z	350	
8	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-23T03:56:00.000Z	1	0	0	0	Cork, Ireland	False	2008-01-09T13:38:16.000Z	12358	
9	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-23T03:56:00.000Z	1	0	0	0	Cork, Ireland	False	2008-01-09T13:38:16.000Z	12358	
10	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-23T03:56:00.000Z	1	0	0	0	Cork, Ireland	False	2008-01-09T13:38:16.000Z	12358	
11	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-23T03:56:00.000Z	1	0	0	0	Cork, Ireland	False	2008-01-09T13:38:16.000Z	12358	
12	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-23T03:56:00.000Z	1	0	0	0	Cork, Ireland	False	2008-01-09T13:38:16.000Z	12358	
13	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-23T03:56:00.000Z	1	0	0	0	Cork, Ireland	False	2008-01-09T13:38:16.000Z	12358	
14	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-23T03:56:00.000Z	1	0	0	0	Cork, Ireland	False	2008-01-09T13:38:16.000Z	12358	
15	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-23T03:56:00.000Z	1	0	0	0	Cork, Ireland	False	2008-01-09T13:38:16.000Z	12358	
16	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-23T03:56:00.000Z	1	0	0	0	Cork, Ireland	False	2008-01-09T13:38:16.000Z	12358	
17	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-23T03:56:00.000Z	1	0	0	0	Cork, Ireland	False	2008-01-09T13:38:16.000Z	12358	
18	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-23T03:56:00.000Z	1	0	0	0	Cork, Ireland	False	2008-01-09T13:38:16.000Z	12358	
19	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-23T03:56:00.000Z	1	0	0	0	Cork, Ireland	False	2008-01-09T13:38:16.000Z	12358	
20	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-23T03:56:00.000Z	1	0	0	0	Cork, Ireland	False	2008-01-09T13:38:16.000Z	12358	
21	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-23T03:56:00.000Z	1	0	0	0	Cork, Ireland	False	2008-01-09T13:38:16.000Z	12358	
22	en	Bar with a name like 'Woodcock'	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	9	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	
23	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	
24	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	
25	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	
26	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	
27	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	
28	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	
29	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	
30	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	
31	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	
32	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	
33	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	
34	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	
35	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	
36	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	
37	en	RT @heatherowenp: I mean, why would y	Twitter for iPhone	2017-12-22T13:29:50.000Z	0	0	0	0	London, England	True	2008-12-11T12:29:25.000Z	99852	

Figure 24 Data collection sample

Figure 25 SBC keywords for twitter

Figure 26 Yearwise count of tweets

9.2.1 Pseudonymization and Anonymization techniques to handle data privacy for collected data in perception extraction architecture pipeline

Pseudonymization is defined in the GDPR as: *“the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person.”*

By contrast, “anonymization” refers to an even stronger form of de-identification. ISO Technical Specification ISO/TS 25237 defines anonymization as: *“a process that removes the association between the identifying data and the data subject”*. Also, in Opinion 05/2014 on Anonymisation Techniques by The Article 29 Working Party, we can read that to meet the standards of anonymization: *“the data must be stripped of sufficient elements such that the data subject can no longer be identified. More precisely, that data must be processed in such a way that it can no longer be used to identify a natural person by using ‘all the means likely reasonably to be used’ by either the controller or a third party. An important factor is that the processing must be irreversible.”*

The aim of processing tweets in the context of METICOS project is to retrieve any tweets publicly posted about Smart Border Control Technologies and to mine the opinion, sentiment and acceptance of Twitter users related to these technologies. Through social media, users share self-expressions, opinions or general thoughts and publicly self-reported activities; these are posted more spontaneously through social media, no guidance needed, and the information provided could be used from context-aware systems. When creating an account on Twitter, the data subjects agree with the terms and conditions of the Twitter’s privacy policy³¹ according to which “By publicly posting content when you Tweet, you are directing us to disclose that information as broadly as possible, including through our APIs, and directing those accessing the information through our APIs to do the same”. A more detailed and complete framework for using Twitter data for research purposes and privacy issues around it is available in Deliverable D1.4 and D3.1 of the METICOS project. Particularly Table 16 and 17 of D3.1 details the conditions for using Twitter data for research purposes. Further Twitter’s privacy police states: “To facilitate the fast global dissemination of Tweets to people around the world, we use technology like application programming interfaces (APIs) and embeds to make that information available to websites, apps, and others for their use - for example, displaying Tweets on a news website or analysing what people say on Twitter.”

In WP6, The Twitter data that we collected for performing perception extraction mainly consists of two types of personal data information (i.e., Tweet ID and Tweet Text) which could be possibly used to identify the original user who posted the relevant tweets. Under the light of explanations above and related to privacy concerns of the use of Twitter data, we performed the steps provided below. This way we ensure that the privacy of the users from whom the Twitter data is protected while during carrying out the first set of experiments for implementing the perception extraction architecture pipeline.

1. We stripped/removed the “Tweet ID” column from our collected data as per the anonymization guidelines discussed above because we are not doing any kind of processing on it for perception extraction.
2. It is difficult to anonymize or pseudonymize the “Tweet Text” as this is the core data which we need to perform perception extraction directly on. Also, this is the public data as the users of the tweets have given consent to the Twitter to publish it publicly on its platform. Therefore, we process this data in our perception extraction architecture, but we do not, and we will not share the exact “Tweet Text” to the border control authorities, METICOS consortium partners and any other third parties outside the METICOS consortium while reporting and disseminating the work related to the extraction of perceptions and perceptions extract in the form of deliverables, scientific publications or any other

³¹ The Twitter privacy policy is available at https://cdn.cms-twdigitalassets.com/content/dam/legal-twitter/site-assets/privacy-june-18th-2020/Twitter_Privacy_Policy_EN.pdf

presentations. We will only report the extracted perceptions in the form of aggregated results.

3. The collected personal data will be deleted once the perception extraction architecture is trained and tested to extract perceptions with reasonable accuracy such that it can be integrated into the METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit.

9.2.2 Possible bias in data collection

The major possible bias in collecting data from Twitter or other social media platforms is the adversarial collection of data[194]. Furthermore, the data collection from online social media platforms like Twitter is regulated by platforms itself which defines the type of data that can be collected for individual users through the Twitter API like tweet text, location, date of tweet posted, etc. The access rights (public/private) for the possible data that can be fetched from the Twitter is set by the users who posted the tweet. Considering this, below are some of the biases that frequently occur when collecting data from online social media platforms.

1) Programmatic access to the data through APIs is often limited

Social media platforms like Twitter provide APIs to collect/access data but they set certain limitations in terms of various aspects like quantity of data to be collected, time frame limitations for data collection and set of limited query parameters to access the data [195, 196]. How the different versions of Twitter API reflect this bias is shown in the section 3.2.2(a). The main bias which occurs here is related to not being able to collect enough representative data for any topic or event which could ultimately lead to bias in overall analysis of the collected data.

Solution → Right now, we are working on data collection from Twitter, and we resolved this bias by using “Twitter Academic Research API”. The main benefits of this API are:

- It provides historical as well as real-time tweets data collection.
- It gives access for historical data in the form of full-archive search from the complete twitter database.
- It supports advanced query parameter language to get more precise results of data collection.
- The monthly limit for data collection using this API is 10 million, which leads to a very good amount of data.
- It is free but first we need to apply and explain to the twitter how we will be using the data to get consent and proper API keys from the twitter.

We applied and received access for this API to use for the METICOS project. All the above benefits serve the purpose for resolving possible bias discussed at the start of the paragraph.

2) The social media platform may not capture all activities of users

The social media platforms usually capture those activities of users which are more in interest for the platform itself such as what is being posted/written, purchased, liked, etc. by the users on the platform. The platforms usually do not capture the information such as what users are reading or watching until users hit any like or comment. However, reading or watching anything also says something about the user behaviors and here the bias occurs that the data social media platforms capture for the users is only the actual activities performed by users [197, 198].

Solution → The main purpose of collecting data in T6.2 is for understanding and extracting user perceptions which is only dependent on what users are writing, commenting, liking, etc. Therefore, this bias has not any effect on our purpose of the data collection.

3) Sampling strategies are often opaque

Different social media platforms have different sampling strategies to limit what and how much data we can collect from the available public data through the APIs. For example, an Twitter API can return k number of tweets based on our query parameters but how those k tweets are sampled create the bias related to either the data is sampled through most relevant, more recent, etc. [195, 197].

Solution → The Twitter Academic Research API that we are using for T6.2 has different ways to collect data: 1) full-archive search data, 2) recent 7 days search data and 3) filtered stream search data. All these ways return the complete data irrespective of any sampling strategy.

4) The data collection APIs might not have such query parameters available which we want to use

Online social media platforms APIs supports several types of query parameters to query data such as geographical locations, query keywords, time intervals, combination of these, etc. Sometimes it happens that the required query parameters for particular task are not supported by the APIs which leads to bias or data loss in the resulting dataset [194].

Solution → The version of Twitter API that we are working for T6.2 contains almost all the important and relevant query parameters options such as query, start time, end time, geo location (user-based, text-based), language, like count, reply count, retweet count, etc. This set of parameters is more than enough to resolve the relevant bias.

5) The population is not the representative of the real-world users

Most of the times the demographics like location of the Twitter users posting the tweets are unknown until the users explicitly make them available while posting the tweets. This results into the bias of over or under representation of certain demographic groups while collecting the data [199].

Solution → We are aware of under-representation of certain demographic groups on Twitter and that we will communicate about this limitation to the users of the METICOS platform & we also will consider other data sources than Twitter in METICOS

9.2.3 Possible bias in data pre-processing

The data pre-processing pipeline may affect the overall data quality, its structure and representation. The possible biases that may occur in data pre-processing are related to data cleaning and aggregation [200, 201].

1) Text pre-processing/cleaning operations may bound certain analysis

The typical text pre-processing/cleaning operations applied on raw data from social media platforms are listed in the section 4.1.3 above. The most common operations listed in that section are

related to the removal of stop words or punctuations. Usually, this text pre-processing is performed to remove irrelevant content which do not contribute to any purpose while understanding the text. However, for example stop words/punctuations do not contribute to understanding sentiment of the text but they can contribute to understanding if a text is representing any question or suggestion. Therefore, performing text pre-processing/cleaning irrespective of the objective that needs to be achieved by analysing the text possibly leads to the bias in text pre-processing/cleaning [202-204].

Solution → We applied several text pre-processing/cleaning steps to our collected data from the Twitter as mentioned in the section 4.1.3. However, the perception extraction pipeline shown in the Figure 20 contains several components which works towards extracting subjectivity, sentiment, intention, aspect, keywords from the text. To avoid the above text pre-processing/cleaning bias we performed selected pre-processing techniques based on the component involved for analysing the text. For example: we removed stop words when processing text for sentiment analysis, but we did not remove any stop words/punctuations when processing text for the intention detection component.

9.3 Experiments

This section explains the individual experimental details for each of the component involved in perception extraction pipeline as shown in Figure 20 above. We have listed the possible bias that can occur while working on machine learning, deep learning, predictive modelling in the section 9.3.1, which reflects the possible biases for all the components involved in perception extraction architecture.

Note* all the conducted experiments are at preliminary stage and based on acquired knowledge from the SoTA as well as gaps identified in the above sections of the document.

9.3.1 Possible bias in experiments

All the experiments involved in the perception extraction architecture pipeline are more often related to the predictions and inferences related techniques. Therefore, this section will discuss possible bias that can occur when working with methodologies or techniques related to predictive machine learning as well as deep learning. The possible bias in predictive/inference for social media data occurs due to the difficulty in understanding political orientations [205], user moods [206] or sometimes user locations [207]. For any given topic, users with different moods and locations talk differently about the same specific topic.

1) There are performance variations across and within datasets

According to the no-lunch-free-theorem [208], no single predictive model works well on all kind of datasets. Even a very best predictive model can introduce errors or pitfalls based on a specific dataset, data classes or users [209, 210]. Also, the performance of these predictive models is highly linked with the pre-processing steps performed on the data [211].

Solution → The experiments performed for perception extraction pipeline are only related to the specific domain of border control technologies. The major drawback we have right now is the unavailability of labelled data, benchmark datasets and existing trained models on this specific domain. Therefore, we have a very good space available to create our own domain specific datasets for different set of experiments involved in perception extraction pipeline using manual human-based or

automatic machine-based approaches. This can easily resolve the above bias related to the datasets and performance variations as the datasets and trained models will be only used in the specific domain of border control technologies. We are planning to work on this as a next step for T6.2 and outcomes of this work will be reported in the D6.3.

2) The composition of test and training data samples impacts the results

The distribution of training and test samples in the predictive modelling highly impacts the results of the predictive model. Also, the selection of training and test samples while building and evaluating the predictive model is a kind of bias which sometimes result in incorrect ~~wrong~~ understandings by the model as the model is not exposed to complete data while training or evaluation [205, 212].

Solution → For our set of experiments, we are trying to handle this bias by working on 1) k-fold cross validation and 2) batching in train/test split while training and evaluating the predictive models involved in different components of the perception extraction pipeline.

3) The imbalance of data samples between different class labels used for prediction

The data imbalance in samples for different class labels while developing predictive models is a very frequent problem which always leads to the bias in training of the models and make the predictive models more align towards class labels having majority of the data samples [72]. For example: the predictive model trained on sentiment prediction with highest data samples of positive class always tends towards good prediction for positive but not for negative class.

Solution → There are many under sampling and over sampling techniques like SMOTE, which helps to avoid this bias while training predictive models. However, for our set of experiments we are planning to use recent text generation techniques like LSTM, GPT-2 to generate synthetic social media data from the real collected social media data to resolve data imbalance problem while training the predictive models. We did similar type of work and reported the results in [72], which encouraged us to follow this approach for handling this bias.

9.3.2 Subjectivity Classification

For subjectivity classification, we acquired a benchmark dataset labelled into two categories: 1) subjective, 2) objective. The dataset was related to general user reviews related to different domains. We cleaned the dataset using preprocessing steps defined in Figure 20. Next, we divided the dataset into two sets: 1) train and 2) test. The train set was used to train the ML model to classify the new text as subjective or objective. The test was used to evaluate the performance of ML model. As, there is no single ML model which works best of every data therefore we used one of the python libraries “AutoSkLearn³²” to select the best model according to our data. This library has variety of ML models implemented along with different technical parameters. Once, we provided our train and test data to AutoSkLearn it resulted into the best fitted model, and it was “RandomForest” ML model.

Finally, we used the SBC tweets dataset collected in the section 9.2, preprocessed it and predicted its subjectivity using the best trained model (i.e., RandomForest). The results of subjectivity classification are discussed in the section 9.4. The experimental flow of subjectivity classification is given in Figure 27.

³² <https://automl.github.io/auto-sklearn/master/>

Figure 27 Flow of subjectivity classification technique

9.3.3 Intent Classification

For intent classification, we faced two major challenges, 1) no pre-defined intents for border control technologies and 2) no prior dataset available. To overcome these challenges and to start preliminary experiments to see how intent is linked with perception extraction for border control technologies; we selected “Zero-shot Learning Model [213]”. Zero-shot learning model performs text classification by training the classification model on a set of class labels and then re-using the trained model with new/different class labels. For our work, we used a pre-trained zero-shot learning model created by hugging face³³. The model is already trained on big Wikipedia corpus text along with training labels from the English vocabulary. First, we defined our own set of intents such as: promotion, information, complaint, questions, suggestion and request. Next, we used the SBC tweets dataset collected in the section 9.2 and preprocessed it. Finally, we input SBC tweets data along with set of defined intents to classify each of the tweet into one of the intents. The list of intents used for classification contains **promotion, information, complaint, question, suggestion and request**. The results of intent classification with their mapping into perception extraction are given in section 9.2. The experimental flow of intent classification using zero-shot learning model is given in Figure 28.

Figure 28 Flow of intent classification technique

9.3.4 Sentiment Analysis

For sentiment analysis, the major challenge is the unavailability of data tagged into different sentiments (e.g. positive, negative, and neutral) for the border control technologies. Therefore, we selected four different automatic sentiment label generation techniques and evaluated them on IMDB sentiment dataset with ground truth sentiment labels. This dataset one of the benchmark dataset for

³³ https://huggingface.co/transformers/master/main_classes/pipelines.html#transformers.ZeroShotClassificationPipeline

sentiment analysis in the literature. Based on majority voting, we selected “Flair” as a sentiment labels generation technique. Next, we trained a “BERT” based supervised transformer model to train a sentiment prediction model. Next, we evaluated the trained model again on IMDB dataset ground truth sentiment labels. The flow of the proposed sentiment analysis technique is given in Figure 29. Finally, we applied this complete flow to the collected SBC tweets data (section 9.2) which were without the sentiment labels. The results of the sentiment analysis techniques are discussed in the section 9.4. We have also submitted a conference paper from the proposed approach in “Northern Light Deep Learning (NLDL – 2022)” conference and it is currently under review. Once, we receive any decision on the submitted paper, we will share more details on the experimental flow.

Figure 29 Flow of sentiment analysis technique

9.3.5 Keyword/Keyphrase Extraction

For keyword/keyphrase extraction, we used the most recent technique from the SoTA which is “KeyBERT [214]”. It is a minimal keyword/keyphrase extraction technique based on BERT based transformers model. It was developed by Maarten Grootendorst [215]. First, we used the SBC tweets dataset collected in the section 9.2 and preprocessed it. Next, we input SBC tweets data to the KeyBERT model to extract the important keywords/keyphrases. We only selected top 10 keywords having keyword score greater than 0.4. Finally, it returns the remaining keyword/keyphrases. The results of keyword/keyphrase extraction with their mapping into perception extraction are given in the section 9.4. The experimental flow of keyword/keyphrase extraction using KeyBERT model is given in Figure 30.

Figure 30 Flow of keyword/keyphrase extraction technique

9.3.6 Aspect Classification

For aspect classification, again we faced two major challenges, 1) no pre-defined aspects for border control technologies and 2) no prior dataset available. To overcome these challenges and to start preliminary experiments to see how aspects are linked with perception extraction for border control technologies; we selected again “Zero-shot Learning Model”. For our work, we used a pre-trained zero-shot learning model created by hugging face³⁴. First, we defined our own set of aspects such as: speed,

³⁴ https://huggingface.co/transformers/master/main_classes/pipelines.html#transformers.ZeroShotClassificationPipeline

UI design, interface, malfunctions and general. Next, we used the SBC tweets dataset collected in the section 9.2 and preprocessed it. Finally, we input SBC tweets data along with set of defined aspects to classify each of the tweet into one of the aspects. The results of aspect classification with their mapping into perception extraction are given in the section 9.4. The experimental flow of aspect classification using zero-shot learning model is given in *Figure 31*.

Figure 31 Flow of aspect classification technique

9.4 Results

This section discusses some of the preliminary results obtained using perception extraction pipeline for border control technologies given in Figure 20.

9.4.1 Bias in perception extraction results

This section discusses the possible biases that can occur while reporting the results from the experiments conducted for perception extraction from the social media data. The results, interpretation or findings are highly dependent on what type of data is being used with what type of experiments [216]. Generally, how the evaluation of the experiments is done leads to the different type of biases in reporting or interpretation of the findings. The possible biases that may occur are:

1) Location-based bias for perception extraction results

We are collecting user tweets related to border control technologies based on defined keywords in previous sections. Along with tweet text, we are also retrieving location of the user who posted the tweet to understand from what parts of the world how the perception varies for border control technologies. The possible bias here is: if a predictive model is only trained on tweet text for predicting sentiment for border control technologies then the type of tweets from locations where the number of tweets is in majority will ultimately results in bias for perception extraction [217].

Solution → Because, we also have location parameter available for the collected tweet therefore in the next steps of perception extraction experiments we are planning to include this parameter as well while training predictive models for performing different experiments in perception extraction architecture. For example: training a sentiment prediction model not only based on tweet text as input but also including location of the tweet to reduce location-based bias for perception extraction results.

2) Performance evaluation metrics bias

There are several performance evaluation metrics for predicting models. Some of them are already mentioned in the section 4.1.1 such as precision, recall, accuracy, etc. The most widely used metric is the accuracy but it tends towards bias which can occur due to the data imbalance between

classes. The accuracy will go higher if the data in one class is high in number and ultimately gives\leads to bias in the overall predicted perception extraction results [207, 218].

Solution → Except accuracy, we are also considering precision, recall and sensitivity-based evaluation metrics which reveal performance of predictive models on each individual class labels. Based on these performance metrics, we are planning to optimize our experiments related to perception extraction. Hence, improving the experiments will result in the reduction of this bias in reporting of the predicted results.

9.4.2 Perception Extraction Results

Figure 32 shows the distribution of the user tweets based on two sentiments, positive and negative. Majority of the tweets predicted negative with 61% from overall test data for SBC technologies. However, 39% of the tweets predicted positive. Furthermore, to relate predicted sentiments more to user perceptions, user profile and demographics, we also performed the observations described below. First, we investigated into the question of what the most frequent locations of the users who have posted on Twitter concerning SBC technologies are. Figure 33 shows the most frequent user locations based on the tweets counts. Here we can see that the highest number of tweets are from United Kingdom. Additionally,

Figure 34 shows the distribution of the positive and negative user sentiments for SBC technologies based on their locations. Again, United Kingdom has the highest number of tweets with a total of 154 negative tweets and 72 positive tweets.

Next, we visualize the year wise count of tweets for SBC technologies in whole as well as the division of the tweets into positive and negative sentiments.

Year Wise SBC Tweets Distribution

Figure 35 shows that the highest number of tweets were posted in 2019. This makes sense because in the year 2020 and 2021, most of the travels stopped due to the COVID-19 pandemic worldwide. Additionally, Figure 36 shows the distribution year wise for positive and negative tweets. Again, the year 2019 has the highest number of tweets with 565 tweets as negative and 407 tweets as positive.

Finally, we also extracted perceptions related to the aspects and intents as well for border control technologies.

Figure 39 shows the perceptions of users related to different aspects of the border control technologies. The highest no. of tweets belongs to the aspect “Interface” with 36%. Additionally, we also visualized the positive and negative sentiment distribution for each of the aspect as well. There are 297 and 244 tweets positive and negative for the “Interface” aspect, respectively. Figure 40 shows the perceptions of the users related to different intents of the border control technologies. Overall, most of the users have raised questions for border control technologies as the overall no. of tweets belong to “question” intent with total 691 tweets.

Figure 32 Predicted sentiments distribution

Figure 33 Most frequent user locations

Figure 34 Most frequent locations-based user sentiments

Year Wise SBC Tweets Distribution

Figure 35 Year wise tweets distribution

Figure 36 Year-wise sentiments distribution

Figure 39 Aspect classification with sentiments results

Figure 40 Intent classification results

Overall, the possible risks from the identified biases in perception extraction from social media data are the incorrect and low-quality data, getting less amount of data, not receiving the data necessary for the analysis, not having representative samples of the data in general, real-world users, problems in the cleaned data and bias in the training process of the predictive models. The possible mitigation measures to resolve these risks are the use of tools like GoogleTrends to identify the correctness/popularity of the relevant keywords over the web, identification of what data cleaning steps are necessary for what kind of process, use of text-generation techniques to resolve the risks of biased training in predictive models involved in the perception extraction architecture. We also

received the access to “Twitter Academic Search API” which also helps to mitigate the few of the above identified risks as well.

10 Relevance of the results in T6.3

The overall METICOS Social Sensing composes of three modules, namely Socio-Cultural Framework Module, METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit and Agent based Simulations Module. The overall architecture receives data that is collected both online and through physical means. The online data sources are Online Social Networks (OSNs) and the physical data sources are in the form of data to be collected at the pilot sites from the pilots, data to be collected from borders (possibly real-time and in the form of traveller/BCP satisfaction, travel documents, etc.), data as SBC technology requirements (such as UI design, process flow, usability, security, trust, etc.) and data coming from BCP\Traveler Questionnaires carried out by WP5.

Socio-Cultural Framework Module (SCFM): This is the module which interfaces the online and physical data sources and identifies patterns (rules) in the data and extract profiles and demographics of persons using borders (travelers) and persons working at the borders (border staff). The rules may be both hands crafted from the data available and also can be automatically extracted from data using machine and deep learning techniques. We estimate rules to be in the form of “person profile → a type of perception”. An example synthetic rule would be “a person over age of 80 perceives the biometrics based verification technology difficult to use”. The rules and the profiles extracted from the data sources are provided as input to the Social Sensing Toolkit Module.

Social Sensing Toolkit Module (SSTM): This is the module which mainly extracts perceptions of the travelers and border staff using the techniques explained in the earlier pages of this document. The same data sources are used as inputs to this module as well as the profiles and rules received from the SCFM. Once the perceptions are extracted, these perceptions are paired with profiles coming from the SCFM. That is, we generate a pool of (profile, perception) pairs which will be used for training and validating the Agent based Simulations Module along with the rules already obtained in the SCFM.

The Agent based Simulations Module (ABSM): the idea behind making simulations is twofold: 1) providing a system where actually we can demonstrate that certain profiles are framed by certain perceptions grounded in the data analysis performed in SCFM and SSTM modules. 2) Once we have the system that can mimic the perceptions of various types of profiles in a realistic way, it can be used to mimic the perceptions of profiles that has not been met before given a set of technologies. That is we can predict border crossing technology acceptance of various users\profiles.

This way we can identify whether age, education level, other types of demographics, crowdedness of the BCP, delays with flights, etc. cause variations in technology acceptance decisions, and furthermore how and why.

As per today, we do not have any data received from most of the sources listed as data sources in Figure 41, to carry the work. For that reason, we have both collected data from Twitter and also created synthetic data sets to represent rules, and perception and profile pairs for our work to begin. Initial trainings of the Agent based simulations are carried by using these data. In these simulations, we have defined three types of agents: travelers who are passing border crossings, border staff, and the border

control technologies. The further details of the experiments (the methodologies for rule, profile and demographics extraction) carried out in the ABSM is explained in the earlier sections of this report already.

We have also identified synthetic scenarios for exploring which profiles lead to what kind of technology acceptance decisions. Next step will be to align with the actual scenarios of the METICOS project whose details will be given in D6.3. Along with data to be received from the other unexplored data sources, we will increase the accuracy of technology prediction decisions of the agent-based simulations module.

Figure 41 Overall METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit Architecture

11 Conclusion

As has been explained in this deliverable, we have done an in-depth analysis of literature and methods to collect and analyse online social media data for perception extraction. We have designed a perception extraction architecture for border control technologies and carried out initial experiments with data collected from Twitter. The results of perception extraction work were encouraging as per the techniques we have selected for use.

Our next step is to do the work related to profile extraction and matching the profile and perception pairs to further train and validate Agent based simulations. The next step will also include data collection from other sources in addition to data collected from Twitter to extract rules and (profile, perception) pairs.

References

1. *Twitter - Statistics & Facts | Statista [Internet].* 24/09/2021]; Available from: <https://www.statista.com/topics/737/twitter/>.
2. Backstrom, L., et al. *Characterizing and curating conversation threads: expansion, focus, volume, re-entry.* in *Proceedings of the sixth ACM international conference on Web search and data mining.* 2013.
3. Shen, J.H. and F. Rudzicz. *Detecting anxiety through reddit.* in *Proceedings of the Fourth Workshop on Computational Linguistics and Clinical Psychology—From Linguistic Signal to Clinical Reality.* 2017.
4. Lee, D.H. and P. Brusilovsky. *Using self-defined group activities for improving recommendations in collaborative tagging systems.* in *Proceedings of the fourth ACM conference on Recommender systems.* 2010.
5. Horváth, T. and S. Wrobel, *Learning from Structured Data,* in *Encyclopedia of Machine Learning,* C. Sammut and G.I. Webb, Editors. 2010, Springer US: Boston, MA. p. 580-584.
6. Eberendu, A., *Unstructured Data: an overview of the data of Big Data.* International Journal of Computer Trends and Technology, 2016. **38**: p. 46-50.
7. Zhang, L., N. Li, and Z. Li. *An Overview on Supervised Semi-structured Data Classification.* in *2021 IEEE 8th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA).* 2021. IEEE.
8. Mahto, D.K. and L. Singh. *A dive into Web Scraper world. in 2016 3rd International Conference on Computing for Sustainable Global Development (INDIACom).* 2016. IEEE.
9. Preis, T., H.S. Moat, and H.E. Stanley, *Quantifying trading behavior in financial markets using Google Trends.* Scientific reports, 2013. **3**(1): p. 1-6.
10. Choi, H. and H. Varian, *Predicting the present with Google Trends.* Economic record, 2012. **88**: p. 2-9.
11. Carneiro, H.A. and E. Mylonakis, *Google trends: a web-based tool for real-time surveillance of disease outbreaks.* Clinical infectious diseases, 2009. **49**(10): p. 1557-1564.
12. De Gagne, J.C., et al., *A qualitative analysis of nursing students' tweets during the COVID-19 pandemic.* Nursing & Health Sciences, 2021. **23**(1): p. 273-278.
13. Contreras, D., *Social Media in Emergency Management & Post-Disaster Recovery.*
14. Jones, W.T., et al. *Interoperable Application Programming Interfaces for Computer Aided Engineering Applications.* in *AIAA Scitech 2021 Forum.* 2021.
15. Mossberger, K., Y. Wu, and J. Crawford, *Connecting citizens and local governments? Social media and interactivity in major US cities.* Government Information Quarterly, 2013. **30**(4): p. 351-358.
16. Berry, D.M., *The computational turn: Thinking about the digital humanities.* Culture machine, 2011. **12**.
17. Pushpam, C.A. and J.G. Jayanthi, *Overview on data mining in social media.* International Journal of Computer Sciences and Engineering, 2017. **5**(11): p. 147-157.
18. Camacho, D., M.V. Luzón, and E. Cambria, *New trends and applications in social media analytics.* 2021, Elsevier.
19. Balan, S. and J. Rege, *Mining for social media: Usage patterns of small businesses.* Business Systems Research: International journal of the Society for Advancing Innovation and Research in Economy, 2017. **8**(1): p. 43-50.
20. Smolensky, P., *Connectionist AI, symbolic AI, and the brain.* Artificial Intelligence Review, 1987. **1**(2): p. 95-109.
21. Rebalá, G., A. Ravi, and S. Churiwala, *Machine Learning Definition and Basics,* in *An Introduction to Machine Learning.* 2019, Springer. p. 1-17.
22. Quinlan, J.R., *C4. 5: programs for machine learning.* 2014: Elsevier.
23. Whelan, E., A.N. Islam, and S. Brooks, *Applying the SOBC paradigm to explain how social media overload affects academic performance.* Computers & Education, 2020. **143**: p. 103692.
24. Alpaydin, E., *Introduction to machine learning.* 2020: MIT press.

25. Rebala, G., A. Ravi, and S. Churiwala, *Learning Models*, in *An Introduction to Machine Learning*. 2019, Springer International Publishing: Cham. p. 19-23.
26. Cunningham, P., M. Cord, and S.J. Delany, *Supervised Learning*, in *Machine Learning Techniques for Multimedia: Case Studies on Organization and Retrieval*, M. Cord and P. Cunningham, Editors. 2008, Springer Berlin Heidelberg: Berlin, Heidelberg. p. 21-49.
27. Hastie, T., R. Tibshirani, and J. Friedman, *Overview of supervised learning*, in *The elements of statistical learning*. 2009, Springer. p. 9-41.
28. Rebala, G., A. Ravi, and S. Churiwala, *Classification*, in *An Introduction to Machine Learning*. 2019, Springer International Publishing: Cham. p. 57-66.
29. Mountrakis, G., J. Im, and C. Ogole, *Support vector machines in remote sensing: A review*. ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing, 2011. **66**(3): p. 247-259.
30. Ting, S., W. Ip, and A.H. Tsang, *Is Naive Bayes a good classifier for document classification*. International Journal of Software Engineering and Its Applications, 2011. **5**(3): p. 37-46.
31. Safavian, S.R. and D. Landgrebe, *A survey of decision tree classifier methodology*. IEEE transactions on systems, man, and cybernetics, 1991. **21**(3): p. 660-674.
32. Chen, J., et al., *A parallel random forest algorithm for big data in a spark cloud computing environment*. IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems, 2016. **28**(4): p. 919-933.
33. Harshvardhan, G., et al., *A comprehensive survey and analysis of generative models in machine learning*. Computer Science Review, 2020. **38**: p. 100285.
34. Rebala, G., A. Ravi, and S. Churiwala, *Regressions*, in *An Introduction to Machine Learning*. 2019, Springer International Publishing: Cham. p. 25-40.
35. Asur, S. and B.A. Huberman. *Predicting the future with social media*. in *2010 IEEE/WIC/ACM international conference on web intelligence and intelligent agent technology*. 2010. IEEE.
36. Criminisi, A., J. Shotton, and E. Konukoglu, *Decision forests: A unified framework for classification, regression, density estimation, manifold learning and semi-supervised learning*. Foundations and trends® in computer graphics and vision, 2012. **7**(2-3): p. 81-227.
37. Hastie, T., R. Tibshirani, and J. Friedman, *Unsupervised learning*, in *The elements of statistical learning*. 2009, Springer. p. 485-585.
38. Rebala, G., A. Ravi, and S. Churiwala, *Clustering*, in *An Introduction to Machine Learning*. 2019, Springer International Publishing: Cham. p. 67-76.
39. Hamerly, G. and C. Elkan, *Learning the k in k-means*. Advances in neural information processing systems, 2003. **16**: p. 281-288.
40. Zhu, X. and A.B. Goldberg, *Introduction to semi-supervised learning*. Synthesis lectures on artificial intelligence and machine learning, 2009. **3**(1): p. 1-130.
41. T.K, B., C.S.R. Annavarapu, and A. Bablani, *Machine learning algorithms for social media analysis: A survey*. Computer Science Review, 2021. **40**: p. 100395.
42. Singh, M., D. Bansal, and S. Sofat, *Behavioral analysis and classification of spammers distributing pornographic content in social media*. Social Network Analysis and Mining, 2016. **6**(1): p. 1-18.
43. Vafeiadis, T., et al., *A comparison of machine learning techniques for customer churn prediction*. Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory, 2015. **55**: p. 1-9.
44. Stantchev, V., L. Prieto-González, and G. Tamm, *Cloud computing service for knowledge assessment and studies recommendation in crowdsourcing and collaborative learning environments based on social network analysis*. Computers in Human Behavior, 2015. **51**: p. 762-770.
45. Deng, X., et al., *An improved method to construct basic probability assignment based on the confusion matrix for classification problem*. Information Sciences, 2016. **340**: p. 250-261.
46. Goodfellow, I., Y. Bengio, and A. Courville, *Deep learning*. 2016: MIT press.
47. Yegnanarayana, B., *Artificial neural networks*. 2009: PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd.
48. Makantasis, K., et al. *Deep supervised learning for hyperspectral data classification through convolutional neural networks*. in *2015 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (IGARSS)*. 2015. IEEE.

49. Mele, A., *A structural model of dense network formation*. *Econometrica*, 2017. **85**(3): p. 825-850.
50. Albawi, S., T.A. Mohammed, and S. Al-Zawi. *Understanding of a convolutional neural network*. in *2017 International Conference on Engineering and Technology (ICET)*. 2017. Ieee.
51. Merrill, W., et al., *A formal hierarchy of RNN architectures*. arXiv preprint arXiv:2004.08500, 2020.
52. Sundermeyer, M., R. Schlüter, and H. Ney. *LSTM neural networks for language modeling*. in *Thirteenth annual conference of the international speech communication association*. 2012.
53. Xu, G., et al., *Sentiment analysis of comment texts based on BiLSTM*. Ieee Access, 2019. **7**: p. 51522-51532.
54. Valpola, H., *From neural PCA to deep unsupervised learning*, in *Advances in independent component analysis and learning machines*. 2015, Elsevier. p. 143-171.
55. Lange, S. and M. Riedmiller. *Deep auto-encoder neural networks in reinforcement learning*. in *The 2010 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*. 2010. IEEE.
56. Salakhutdinov, R. and G. Hinton. *Deep boltzmann machines*. in *Artificial intelligence and statistics*. 2009. PMLR.
57. Krizhevsky, A., I. Sutskever, and G.E. Hinton, *Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks*. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 2012. **25**: p. 1097-1105.
58. Deng, J., et al. *Imagenet: A large-scale hierarchical image database*. in *2009 IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2009. Ieee.
59. Ouali, Y., C. Hudelot, and M. Tami, *An overview of deep semi-supervised learning*. arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.05278, 2020.
60. Settles, B., *Active learning literature survey*. 2009.
61. Ratner, A., et al., *Weak supervision: the new programming paradigm for machine learning*. Hazy Research. Available via <https://dawn.cs.stanford.edu/2017/07/16/weak-supervision/>. Accessed, 2019: p. 05-09.
62. Guimaraes, R.G., et al., *Age groups classification in social network using deep learning*. IEEE Access, 2017. **5**: p. 10805-10816.
63. Zin, T.T., P. Tin, and H. Hama. *Deep learning model for integration of clustering with ranking in social networks*. in *International Conference on Genetic and Evolutionary Computing*. 2016. Springer.
64. Badjatiya, P., et al. *Deep learning for hate speech detection in tweets*. in *Proceedings of the 26th international conference on World Wide Web companion*. 2017.
65. Pitsilis, G.K., H. Ramampiaro, and H. Langseth, *Detecting offensive language in tweets using deep learning*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1801.04433, 2018.
66. Alali, M., et al. *Multi-layers convolutional neural network for twitter sentiment ordinal scale classification*. in *International Conference on Soft Computing and Data Mining*. 2018. Springer.
67. Shaikh, S., S.M. Daudpotta, and A.S. Imran, *Bloom's Learning Outcomes' Automatic Classification Using LSTM and Pretrained Word Embeddings*. IEEE Access, 2021. **9**: p. 117887-117909.
68. Batra, R., et al., *Evaluating Polarity Trend Amidst the Coronavirus Crisis in Peoples' Attitudes toward the Vaccination Drive*. *Sustainability*, 2021. **13**(10): p. 5344.
69. Xue, D., et al., *Deep learning-based personality recognition from text posts of online social networks*. *Applied Intelligence*, 2018. **48**(11): p. 4232-4246.
70. da Silva, B.B.C. and I. Paraboni. *Personality recognition from Facebook text*. in *International Conference on Computational Processing of the Portuguese Language*. 2018. Springer.
71. Shaikh, S. and S.M. Doudpotta, *Aspects based opinion mining for teacher and course evaluation*. *Sukkur IBA Journal of Computing and Mathematical Sciences*, 2019. **3**(1): p. 34-43.
72. Shaikh, S., et al., *Towards Improved Classification Accuracy on Highly Imbalanced Text Dataset Using Deep Neural Language Models*. *Applied Sciences*, 2021. **11**(2): p. 869.
73. Granaas, M.M., *Simple, applied text parsing*. *Behavior Research Methods, Instruments, & Computers*, 1985. **17**(2): p. 209-216.

74. Kumawat, D. and V. Jain, *POS tagging approaches: a comparison*. International Journal of Computer Applications, 2015. **118**(6).
75. Munoz, M., et al., *A learning approach to shallow parsing*. arXiv preprint cs/0008022, 2000.
76. Rodriguez, C.G., *Parsing Schemata for Practical Text Analysis*. 2011, Citeseer.
77. Guyon, I. and A. Elisseeff, *An introduction to feature extraction*, in *Feature extraction*. 2006, Springer. p. 1-25.
78. Chen, W., et al., *Exploiting meta features for dependency parsing and part-of-speech tagging*. Artificial Intelligence, 2016. **230**: p. 173-191.
79. Blackstock, A. and M. Spitz, *Classifying movie scripts by genre with a MEMM using NLP-Based features*. Citeseer, 2008.
80. Zhang, Y., R. Jin, and Z.-H. Zhou, *Understanding bag-of-words model: a statistical framework*. International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics, 2010. **1**(1-4): p. 43-52.
81. Shi, C.-y., C.-j. Xu, and X.-J. Yang, *Study of TFIDF algorithm*. Journal of Computer Applications, 2009. **29**(6): p. 167-170.
82. Pizarro, J. *Using N-grams to detect Bots on Twitter*. in *CLEF (Working Notes)*. 2019.
83. Kulkarni, A. and A. Shivananda, *Converting text to features*, in *Natural language processing recipes*. 2021, Springer. p. 63-106.
84. Church, K.W., *Word2Vec*. Natural Language Engineering, 2017. **23**(1): p. 155-162.
85. Lau, J.H. and T. Baldwin, *An empirical evaluation of doc2vec with practical insights into document embedding generation*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1607.05368, 2016.
86. Joulin, A., et al., *Fasttext. zip: Compressing text classification models*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1612.03651, 2016.
87. Pennington, J., R. Socher, and C.D. Manning. *Glove: Global vectors for word representation*. in *Proceedings of the 2014 conference on empirical methods in natural language processing (EMNLP)*. 2014.
88. Zhu, H., I.C. Paschalidis, and A. Tahmasebi, *Clinical concept extraction with contextual word embedding*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1810.10566, 2018.
89. Birjali, M., M. Kasri, and A. Beni-Hssane, *A comprehensive survey on sentiment analysis: Approaches, challenges and trends*. Knowledge-Based Systems, 2021: p. 107134.
90. Nandwani, P. and R. Verma, *A review on sentiment analysis and emotion detection from text*. Social Network Analysis and Mining, 2021. **11**(1): p. 1-19.
91. Ahmad, Z., et al., *Borrow from rich cousin: transfer learning for emotion detection using cross lingual embedding*. Expert Systems with Applications, 2020. **139**: p. 112851.
92. Shirsat, V.S., R.S. Jagdale, and S.N. Deshmukh, *Sentence level sentiment identification and calculation from news articles using machine learning techniques*, in *Computing, Communication and Signal Processing*. 2019, Springer. p. 371-376.
93. Pu, X., G. Wu, and C. Yuan, *Exploring overall opinions for document level sentiment classification with structural SVM*. Multimedia Systems, 2019. **25**(1): p. 21-33.
94. Nandhini, M.D.S. and G. Pradeep, *A Hybrid Co-occurrence and Ranking-based Approach for Detection of Implicit Aspects in Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis*. SN Computer Science, 2020. **1**(3): p. 1-9.
95. Khoo, C.S. and S.B. Johnkhan, *Lexicon-based sentiment analysis: Comparative evaluation of six sentiment lexicons*. Journal of Information Science, 2018. **44**(4): p. 491-511.
96. Ye, Q., Z. Zhang, and R. Law, *Sentiment classification of online reviews to travel destinations by supervised machine learning approaches*. Expert systems with applications, 2009. **36**(3): p. 6527-6535.
97. Jain, P.K., R. Pamula, and G. Srivastava, *A systematic literature review on machine learning applications for consumer sentiment analysis using online reviews*. Computer Science Review, 2021. **41**: p. 100413.
98. Pasupa, K. and T.S.N. Ayuthaya, *Thai sentiment analysis with deep learning techniques: A comparative study based on word embedding, POS-tag, and sentic features*. Sustainable Cities and Society, 2019. **50**: p. 101615.

99. Songbo, T. and Z. Jin, *An empirical study of sentiment analysis for Chinese documents*. Expert Systems with Applications, 2008. **34**(4): p. 2622-2629.
100. Moraes, R., J.F. Valiati, and W.P.G. Neto, *Document-level sentiment classification: An empirical comparison between SVM and ANN*. Expert Systems with Applications, 2013. **40**(2): p. 621-633.
101. Tang, D., B. Qin, and T. Liu. *Learning semantic representations of users and products for document level sentiment classification*. in *Proceedings of the 53rd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics and the 7th International Joint Conference on Natural Language Processing (Volume 1: Long Papers)*. 2015.
102. Dahou, A., et al. *Word embeddings and convolutional neural network for arabic sentiment classification*. in *Proceedings of coling 2016, the 26th international conference on computational linguistics: Technical papers*. 2016.
103. Ahuja, R., et al., *The impact of features extraction on the sentiment analysis*. Procedia Computer Science, 2019. **152**: p. 341-348.
104. Untawale, T.M. and G. Choudhari. *Implementation of sentiment classification of movie reviews by supervised machine learning approaches*. in *2019 3rd International Conference on Computing Methodologies and Communication (ICCMC)*. 2019. IEEE.
105. Shamantha, R.B., S.M. Shetty, and P. Rai. *Sentiment analysis using machine learning classifiers: evaluation of performance*. in *2019 IEEE 4th International Conference on Computer and Communication Systems (ICCCS)*. 2019. IEEE.
106. Goularas, D. and S. Kamis. *Evaluation of deep learning techniques in sentiment analysis from twitter data*. in *2019 International Conference on Deep Learning and Machine Learning in Emerging Applications (Deep-ML)*. 2019. IEEE.
107. Nandal, N., R. Tanwar, and J. Pruthi, *Machine learning based aspect level sentiment analysis for Amazon products*. Spatial Information Research, 2020. **28**(5): p. 601-607.
108. Sharma, P. and A. Sharma, *Experimental investigation of automated system for twitter sentiment analysis to predict the public emotions using machine learning algorithms*. Materials Today: Proceedings, 2020.
109. Mukherjee, P., et al., *Effect of Negation in Sentences on Sentiment Analysis and Polarity Detection*. Procedia Computer Science, 2021. **185**: p. 370-379.
110. Boon-Itt, S. and Y. Skunkan, *Public perception of the COVID-19 pandemic on Twitter: Sentiment analysis and topic modeling study*. JMIR Public Health and Surveillance, 2020. **6**(4): p. e21978.
111. Deerwester, S., et al., *Indexing by latent semantic analysis*. Journal of the American society for information science, 1990. **41**(6): p. 391-407.
112. Buckley, C., J. Allan, and G. Salton, *Automatic routing and ad-hoc retrieval using SMART: TREC 2*. NIST SPECIAL PUBLICATION SP, 1994: p. 45-45.
113. Kherwa, P. and P. Bansal, *Topic modeling: a comprehensive review*. EAI Endorsed transactions on scalable information systems, 2020. **7**(24).
114. Paatero, P. and U. Tapper, *Positive matrix factorization: A non-negative factor model with optimal utilization of error estimates of data values*. Environmetrics, 1994. **5**(2): p. 111-126.
115. Lee, D.D. and H.S. Seung, *Learning the parts of objects by non-negative matrix factorization*. Nature, 1999. **401**(6755): p. 788-791.
116. Cooper, G.F. and S. Moral, *Proceedings of the Fourteenth conference on Uncertainty in artificial intelligence*. 1998: Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc.
117. De Finetti, B., *Theory of probability: A critical introductory treatment*. Vol. 6. 2017: John Wiley & Sons.
118. Nguyen, D.Q., et al., *Improving topic models with latent feature word representations*. Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics, 2015. **3**: p. 299-313.
119. Yin, H., et al. *A unified model for stable and temporal topic detection from social media data*. in *2013 IEEE 29th International Conference on Data Engineering (ICDE)*. 2013. IEEE.
120. Xie, W., et al., *Topicsketch: Real-time bursty topic detection from twitter*. IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering, 2016. **28**(8): p. 2216-2229.

121. Cataldi, M., L. Di Caro, and C. Schifanella. *Emerging topic detection on twitter based on temporal and social terms evaluation*. in *Proceedings of the tenth international workshop on multimedia data mining*. 2010.
122. Mottaghinia, Z., et al., *A review of approaches for topic detection in Twitter*. *Journal of Experimental & Theoretical Artificial Intelligence*, 2021. **33**(5): p. 747-773.
123. Gencoglu, O., *Deep representation learning for clustering of health tweets*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1901.00439, 2018.
124. Ma, G., *Tweets classification with bert in the field of disaster management*. Dept. Civil Eng., Stanford Univ., Stanford, CA, USA, Tech. Rep, 2019. **15785631**.
125. Hu, Y., et al. *Short text classification with a convolutional neural networks based method*. in *2018 15th International Conference on Control, Automation, Robotics and Vision (ICARCV)*. 2018. IEEE.
126. Hasan, M., M.A. Orgun, and R. Schwitter, *Real-time event detection from the Twitter data stream using the TwitterNews+ Framework*. *Information Processing & Management*, 2019. **56**(3): p. 1146-1165.
127. Tembhurnikar, S.D. and N.N. Patil. *Topic detection using BNgram method and sentiment analysis on twitter dataset*. in *2015 4th International Conference on Reliability, Infocom Technologies and Optimization (ICRITO)(Trends and Future Directions)*. 2015. IEEE.
128. Sindhu, C., et al., *Subjectivity detection for sentiment analysis on Twitter data*, in *Artificial Intelligence Techniques for Advanced Computing Applications*. 2021, Springer. p. 467-476.
129. Kumar, A. and T.M. Sebastian, *Sentiment analysis on twitter*. *International Journal of Computer Science Issues (IJCSI)*, 2012. **9**(4): p. 372.
130. Ortega, R., A. Fonseca, and A. Montoyo. *SSA-UO: unsupervised Twitter sentiment analysis*. in *Second joint conference on lexical and computational semantics (* SEM)*. 2013.
131. Obuchowski, A., *Transformer-Capsule Model for Intent Detection*. 2020.
132. Casanueva, I., et al., *Efficient intent detection with dual sentence encoders*. arXiv preprint arXiv:2003.04807, 2020.
133. Tur, G., D. Hakkani-Tür, and L. Heck. *What is left to be understood in ATIS?* in *2010 IEEE Spoken Language Technology Workshop*. 2010. IEEE.
134. Larson, S., et al., *An evaluation dataset for intent classification and out-of-scope prediction*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1909.02027, 2019.
135. Cohan, A., et al., *Structural scaffolds for citation intent classification in scientific publications*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1904.01608, 2019.
136. Adekotujo, A.S., et al. *Bi-lingual Intent Classification of Twitter Posts: A Roadmap*. in *International Conference in Software Engineering for Defence Applications*. 2018. Springer.
137. Chen, Q., Z. Zhuo, and W. Wang, *Bert for joint intent classification and slot filling*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1902.10909, 2019.
138. Huang, Q., et al., *Automating intention mining*. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, 2018. **46**(10): p. 1098-1119.
139. Abbet, C., et al., *Churn intent detection in multilingual chatbot conversations and social media*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1808.08432, 2018.
140. Siddiqi, S. and A. Sharan, *Keyword and keyphrase extraction techniques: a literature review*. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 2015. **109**(2).
141. Lahiri, S., S.R. Choudhury, and C. Caragea, *Keyword and keyphrase extraction using centrality measures on collocation networks*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1401.6571, 2014.
142. Zhao, D., et al. *Keyword extraction for social media short text*. in *2017 14th Web Information Systems and Applications Conference (WISA)*. 2017. IEEE.
143. Luhn, H.P., *A statistical approach to mechanized encoding and searching of literary information*. *IBM Journal of research and development*, 1957. **1**(4): p. 309-317.
144. Salton, G. and C. Buckley, *Term-weighting approaches in automatic text retrieval*. *Information processing & management*, 1988. **24**(5): p. 513-523.
145. Cohen, J.D., *Highlights: Language-and domain-independent automatic indexing terms for abstracting*. *Journal of the American society for information science*, 1995. **46**(3): p. 162-174.

146. Matsuo, Y. and M. Ishizuka, *Keyword extraction from a single document using word co-occurrence statistical information*. International Journal on Artificial Intelligence Tools, 2004. **13**(01): p. 157-169.
147. Campos, R., et al. *Yake! collection-independent automatic keyword extractor*. in *European Conference on Information Retrieval*. 2018. Springer.
148. Witten, I.H., et al., *Kea: Practical automated keyphrase extraction*, in *Design and Usability of Digital Libraries: Case Studies in the Asia Pacific*. 2005, IGI global. p. 129-152.
149. Papagiannopoulou, E. and G. Tsoumakas, *A review of keyphrase extraction*. Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery, 2020. **10**(2): p. e1339.
150. Mihalcea, R. and P. Tarau. *Textrank: Bringing order into text*. in *Proceedings of the 2004 conference on empirical methods in natural language processing*. 2004.
151. Mothe, J., F. Ramiandrisoa, and M. Rasolomanana. *Automatic keyphrase extraction using graph-based methods*. in *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Symposium on Applied Computing*. 2018.
152. Wan, X. and J. Xiao. *Single Document Keyphrase Extraction Using Neighborhood Knowledge*. in *AAAI*. 2008.
153. Florescu, C. and C. Caragea. *Positionrank: An unsupervised approach to keyphrase extraction from scholarly documents*. in *Proceedings of the 55th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)*. 2017.
154. Alzaidy, R., C. Caragea, and C.L. Giles. *Bi-LSTM-CRF sequence labeling for keyphrase extraction from scholarly documents*. in *The world wide web conference*. 2019.
155. Wang, Y., et al. *Exploiting topic-based adversarial neural network for cross-domain keyphrase extraction*. in *2018 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining (ICDM)*. 2018. IEEE.
156. Basaldella, M., et al. *Bidirectional lstm recurrent neural network for keyphrase extraction*. in *Italian Research Conference on Digital Libraries*. 2018. Springer.
157. Ye, H. and L. Wang, *Semi-supervised learning for neural keyphrase generation*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1808.06773, 2018.
158. Florescu, C. and W. Jin. *Learning feature representations for keyphrase extraction*. in *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*. 2018.
159. McGregor, S.C., *Social media as public opinion: How journalists use social media to represent public opinion*. Journalism, 2019. **20**(8): p. 1070-1086.
160. Sofalvi, A.J. and C.O. Airhihenbuwa, *An analysis of the relationship between news coverage of health topics and public opinion of the most important health problems in the United States*. Journal of Health Education, 1992. **23**(5): p. 296-300.
161. Krugman, H.E., *The impact of television advertising: Learning without involvement*. Public opinion quarterly, 1965. **29**(3): p. 349-356.
162. Tobin, C., A.R. Moodie, and C. Livingstone, *A review of public opinion towards alcohol controls in Australia*. BMC Public Health, 2011. **11**(1): p. 1-9.
163. D'Andrea, E., et al., *Monitoring the public opinion about the vaccination topic from tweets analysis*. Expert Systems with Applications, 2019. **116**: p. 209-226.
164. Murphy, J., et al., *Social media in public opinion research: Executive summary of the AAPOR task force on emerging technologies in public opinion research*. Public Opinion Quarterly, 2014. **78**(4): p. 788-794.
165. Fishkin, J.S., *Beyond polling alone: the quest for an informed public*. Critical Review, 2006. **18**(1-3): p. 157-165.
166. Bian, J., et al., *Mining Twitter to assess the public perception of the "Internet of Things"*. PloS one, 2016. **11**(7): p. e0158450.
167. Khan, S., et al., *Antecedents of trust in using social media for E-government services: An empirical study in Pakistan*. Technology in Society, 2021. **64**: p. 101400.
168. Huang, M.-h., T. Whang, and L. Xuchuan, *The Internet, social capital, and civic engagement in Asia*. Social Indicators Research, 2017. **132**(2): p. 559.

169. Kang, Y., et al., *The public's opinions on a new school meals policy for childhood obesity prevention in the US: A social media analytics approach*. International journal of medical informatics, 2017. **103**: p. 83-88.
170. Anstead, N. and B. O'Loughlin, *Social media analysis and public opinion: The 2010 UK general election*. Journal of computer-mediated communication, 2015. **20**(2): p. 204-220.
171. Chen, S.-C. and C.-P. Lin, *Understanding the effect of social media marketing activities: The mediation of social identification, perceived value, and satisfaction*. Technological Forecasting and Social Change, 2019. **140**: p. 22-32.
172. Mollema, L., et al., *Disease detection or public opinion reflection? Content analysis of tweets, other social media, and online newspapers during the measles outbreak in The Netherlands in 2013*. Journal of medical Internet research, 2015. **17**(5): p. e3863.
173. Xue, Y., et al., *Relationship discovery in public opinion and actual behavior for social media stock data space*. EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking, 2016. **2016**(1): p. 1-13.
174. Pourebrahim, N., et al., *Understanding communication dynamics on Twitter during natural disasters: A case study of Hurricane Sandy*. International journal of disaster risk reduction, 2019. **37**: p. 101176.
175. Adams-Cohen, N.J., *Policy change and public opinion: Measuring shifting political sentiment with social media data*. American Politics Research, 2020. **48**(5): p. 612-621.
176. Salleh, S.M., *From survey to social media: Public opinion and politics in the age of big data*. Advanced Science Letters, 2017. **23**(11): p. 10696-10700.
177. Dong, X. and Y. Lian, *A review of social media-based public opinion analyses: Challenges and recommendations*. Technology in Society, 2021. **67**: p. 101724.
178. Lokeshkumar, R., O.A. Mishra, and S. Kalra, *Social media data analysis to predict mental state of users using machine learning techniques*. Journal of Education and Health Promotion, 2021. **10**(1): p. 301.
179. Guo, Y., et al., *The application of artificial intelligence and data integration in COVID-19 studies: a scoping review*. Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association, 2021.
180. Luo, J., et al., *Exploring temporal suicidal behavior patterns on social media: Insight from Twitter analytics*. Health informatics journal, 2020. **26**(2): p. 738-752.
181. Valdez, D., et al., *Social media insights into US mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic: longitudinal analysis of twitter data*. Journal of medical Internet research, 2020. **22**(12): p. e21418.
182. Santander, P., et al., *Analyzing social media, analyzing the social? A methodological discussion about the demoscopic and predictive potential of social media*. Quality & Quantity, 2020: p. 1-21.
183. Martinez, L.S., M.-H. Tsou, and B.H. Spitzberg. *A case study in belief surveillance, sentiment analysis, and identification of informational targets for e-cigarettes interventions*. in *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Social Media and Society*. 2019.
184. Saravanan, M. and S.K. Perepu, *Realizing social-media-based analytics for smart agriculture*. The Review of Socionetwork Strategies, 2019. **13**(1): p. 33-53.
185. Chang, Y.-C., C.-H. Ku, and C.-H. Chen, *Social media analytics: Extracting and visualizing Hilton hotel ratings and reviews from TripAdvisor*. International Journal of Information Management, 2019. **48**: p. 263-279.
186. von Hoffen, M., et al., *Leveraging social media to gain insights into service delivery: a study on Airbnb*. Information Systems and e-Business Management, 2018. **16**(2): p. 247-269.
187. Chumwatana, T. and K. Wongkolkitilp. *Using Classification Technique for Customer Relationship Management based on Thai Social Media Data*. in *Proceedings of the 2019 11th International Conference on Computer and Automation Engineering*. 2019.
188. Tian, X., et al., *A new approach of social media analytics to predict service quality: evidence from the airline industry*. Journal of Enterprise Information Management, 2019.
189. Dahal, B., S.A. Kumar, and Z. Li, *Topic modeling and sentiment analysis of global climate change tweets*. Social Network Analysis and Mining, 2019. **9**(1): p. 1-20.

190. Dias, D.S., M.D. Welikala, and N.G. Dias. *Identifying racist social media comments in Sinhala language using text analytics models with machine learning*. in *2018 18th International Conference on Advances in ICT for Emerging Regions (ICTer)*. 2018. IEEE.
191. Barrelet, C.J., S.S. Kuzulugil, and A.B. Bener. *The Twitter Bullishness Index: A Social Media Analytics Indicator for the Stock Market*. in *Proceedings of the 20th International Database Engineering & Applications Symposium*. 2016.
192. Park, S.B., J. Jang, and C.M. Ok, *Analyzing Twitter to explore perceptions of Asian restaurants*. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, 2016.
193. Tufekci, Z. *Big questions for social media big data: Representativeness, validity and other methodological pitfalls*. in *Eighth international AAAI conference on weblogs and social media*. 2014.
194. González-Bailón, S., et al., *Assessing the bias in samples of large online networks*. *Social Networks*, 2014. **38**: p. 16-27.
195. Morstatter, F., et al. *Is the sample good enough? comparing data from twitter's streaming api with twitter's firehose*. in *Seventh international AAAI conference on weblogs and social media*. 2013.
196. Olteanu, A., et al. *Crisislex: A lexicon for collecting and filtering microblogged communications in crises*. in *Eighth international AAAI conference on weblogs and social media*. 2014.
197. Maddock, J., K. Starbird, and R.M. Mason. *Using historical Twitter data for research: Ethical challenges of tweet deletions*. in *CSCW 2015 workshop on ethics for studying sociotechnical systems in a Big Data World*. ACM. 2015.
198. Boyd, D. and K. Crawford, *Critical questions for big data: Provocations for a cultural, technological, and scholarly phenomenon*. *Information, communication & society*, 2012. **15**(5): p. 662-679.
199. Johnson, I., et al. *The Effect of Population and "Structural" Biases on Social Media-based Algorithms: A Case Study in Geolocation Inference Across the Urban-Rural Spectrum*. in *Proceedings of the 2017 CHI conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. 2017.
200. Barocas, S. and A.D. Selbst, *Big data's disparate impact*. *Calif. L. Rev.*, 2016. **104**: p. 671.
201. Poirier, L., *Knowledge Representation in Scruffy Worlds an Ethnography of Semiotic Infrastructure Design Work*. 2018: Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute.
202. Pennebaker, J.W., M.R. Mehl, and K.G. Niederhoffer, *Psychological aspects of natural language use: Our words, our selves*. *Annual review of psychology*, 2003. **54**(1): p. 547-577.
203. Saif, H., et al., *On stopwords, filtering and data sparsity for sentiment analysis of twitter*. 2014.
204. Denny, M.J. and A. Spirling, *Assessing the consequences of text preprocessing decisions*. Available at SSRN, 2016.
205. Cohen, R. and D. Ruths. *Classifying political orientation on Twitter: It's not easy!* in *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*. 2013.
206. Beasley, A. and W. Mason. *Emotional states vs. emotional words in social media*. in *Proceedings of the ACM web science conference*. 2015.
207. Jurgens, D., et al. *Geolocation prediction in twitter using social networks: A critical analysis and review of current practice*. in *Ninth international AAAI conference on web and social media*. 2015.
208. Adam, S.P., et al., *No free lunch theorem: A review*. *Approximation and optimization*, 2019: p. 57-82.
209. Pavalanathan, U. and J. Eisenstein, *Confounds and consequences in geotagged Twitter data*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1506.02275, 2015.
210. Tramèr, F., et al., *Discovering unwarranted associations in data-driven applications with the fairest testing toolkit*. CoRR, abs/1510.02377, 2015.
211. García, S., J. Luengo, and F. Herrera, *Data preprocessing in data mining*. Vol. 72. 2015: Springer.
212. Rao, D., et al. *Classifying latent user attributes in twitter*. in *Proceedings of the 2nd international workshop on Search and mining user-generated contents*. 2010.
213. Socher, R., et al., *Zero-shot learning through cross-modal transfer*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1301.3666, 2013.

214. Giarelis, N., N. Kanakaris, and N. Karacapilidis. *A Comparative Assessment of State-Of-The-Art Methods for Multilingual Unsupervised Keyphrase Extraction*. in *IFIP International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations*. 2021. Springer.
215. Piskorski, J., et al. *Exploring Linguistically-Lightweight Keyword Extraction Techniques for Indexing News Articles in a Multilingual Set-up*. in *Proceedings of the EACL Hackashop on News Media Content Analysis and Automated Report Generation*. 2021.
216. Rost, M., et al. *Representation and communication: Challenges in interpreting large social media datasets*. in *Proceedings of the 2013 conference on Computer supported cooperative work*. 2013.
217. Fraustino, J.D., B. Liu, and Y. Jin, *Social media use during disasters: a review of the knowledge base and gaps*. 2012.
218. Olteanu, A., A.-M. Kermarrec, and K. Aberer. *Comparing the predictive capability of social and interest affinity for recommendations*. in *International Conference on Web Information Systems Engineering*. 2014. Springer.

Appendix

